

1 **Fractal sampling design reveals climate and scale effects on rainforest bird communities in**
2 **central Africa**

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25 **Key words**

26 alpha diversity (alpha points), beta diversity (beta clusters), Congo forests, gamma diversity
27 (gamma fractals), rainfall gradients, species abundance distributions, tropics, effective spatial
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49 **Abstract**

50 Understanding how climate shapes patterns of diversity and community structure across spatial
51 scales is crucial for conservation planning and for testing ecological theory. However, it remains
52 poorly understood whether macroecological patterns of diversity, abundance, and biomass in
53 tropical animal communities are driven primarily by mean climatic conditions or by climatic
54 seasonality, and how the strength of these relationships depends on spatial scale. Here, we
55 examined whether mean conditions or seasonality in precipitation and temperature shape bird
56 community diversity and structure along a rainfall gradient in Central Africa, using a novel
57 nested fractal design that varies effective spatial grain—the realized spatial resolution of
58 biodiversity sampling—while holding spatial extent and basic sampling grain constant. This
59 design allows scale-dependent ecological processes to be disentangled from sampling effects
60 across alternative sampling scenarios. We characterized community patterns and their
61 reorganization across spatial scales using Hill numbers and structural reorganization metrics, and
62 quantified associations between precipitation, temperature, and their seasonalities with
63 community properties (diversity, aggregated abundance, and biomass). Analyses were based on
64 standardized sampling points ($n = 144$) conducted across four distant primary forest sites (>300
65 km apart), using complementary statistical modelling approaches. Diversity profiles and
66 structural reorganization metrics revealed heterogeneous patterns among forest sites, highlighting
67 scale dependence in diversity and community structure. Precipitation showed consistently
68 unimodal relationships with diversity and negative effects on aggregated abundance, but no
69 significant effect on aggregated biomass, whereas temperature effects were generally weaker. In
70 contrast, seasonality in precipitation and temperature significantly influenced community
71 structure. Varying effective spatial grain revealed that diversity responses to climate can be scale-
72 dependent, whereas responses of aggregated abundance and biomass are comparatively consistent

73 across spatial scales. Overall, our results support a key role of climate—particularly precipitation
74 and its seasonality—in shaping macroecological patterns, while also demonstrating that climate
75 alone cannot fully explain community variation across the gradient. By explicitly manipulating
76 effective spatial grain, this study provides a general framework for evaluating scale-dependent
77 macroecological patterns in tropical systems and highlights the value of spatially explicit, multi-
78 scale approaches for monitoring biodiversity change under the Anthropocene

79 **Introduction**

80 Tropical forests harbor the highest biodiversity on Earth, yet their large-scale (macroecological)
81 patterns of diversity and community structure remain poorly understood (Erwin 1991; Jenkins et
82 al. 2013; Seymour et al. 2024).. These include species abundance distributions, and relationships
83 between biomass and diversity (Brown 1995; Gaston and Blackburn 2010). Much of the
84 macroecological literature has focused on latitudinal (Barreto et al. 2021; Chu et al. 2019; Coelho
85 et al. 2025; Hülsmann et al. 2024), altitudinal (Quintero and Jetz 2018; Yang et al. 2025), or
86 temperature gradients (Khaliq et al. 2024; Luukkonen et al. 2024), with far fewer studies
87 conducted in tropical lowland regions (Echeverri et al. 2019; Londoño et al. 2023; Montano-
88 Centellas et al. 2020; Moses et al. 2023). Among the underexplored gradients are tropical
89 lowland climatic gradients, which often show strong variation in precipitation with little variation
90 in temperature (Givnish 1999; Malhi et al. 2004).

91 One of the most influential theories in macroecology is the climate hypothesis (Wright 1983),
92 which posits that community structure (abundance, biomass) and diversity are largely determined
93 by energy (temperature) and water availability (rainfall) (Brown 1995; Currie et al. 2004; Evans
94 et al. 2005; Field et al. 2009; Hawkins et al. 2003). Climate effects may act directly affecting
95 physiological and metabolic responses, and indirectly by modifying trophic group productivity

96 (Coelho et al. 2025; Evans et al. 2005; Storch et al. 2018; Jetz et al. 2008) . Global analyses
97 suggest that water-related variables are particularly important determinants of diversity in the
98 tropics where energy is abundant (Hawkins et al. 2003), a finding supported by many regional
99 studies (e.g. Esquivel-Muelbert et al. 2019; Neves et al. 2020; Tolmos et al. 2022). Seasonality in
100 rainfall and temperature also can influence community structure, (Jarzyna et al. 2021; Keyser et
101 al. 2024; Qian et al. 2023), influencing food resource availability and the temporal length of
102 climate stress. While elevational gradients have often been used to test the climate hypothesis,
103 temperature and rainfall typically covary in those gradients, making it difficult to isolate their
104 individual effects (Ferber et al. 2017; Kessler et al. 2011; McCain 2009; Terborgh 1971).
105 Tropical lowland rainfall gradients, in contrast, show little variation in temperature (and
106 elevation), but exhibit a wide range in precipitation (Malhi et al. 2004). , offering opportunities to
107 explore the influences of rainfall and its seasonality. The responses of tropical bird communities
108 to climatic conditions in regional lowland climatic gradients are not well understood. Previous
109 research suggests that tropical bird diversity and structure are strongly modulated by mean
110 temperature and rainfall, but the influence of their seasonality is less clear. Temperatures tend to
111 dominate the effects on bird diversity in tropical altitudinal gradients (Ferber et al. 2017; Hanz
112 et al. 2019; Jankowski et al. 2009; Terborgh 1971), whereas some research suggest that high
113 water availability (precipitation) positively influences bird diversity in tropical lowlands with low
114 variation in altitude and temperature (Hawkins et al. 2003; Echeverri et al. 2019; Rompré et al.
115 2007). One hypothesis is that more precipitation drives more productivity, enhancing bird
116 diversity indirectly via plant diversity (Hawkins et al. 2003; Evans et al. 2005; Jetz et al. 2008) or
117 directly influencing metabolism and physiological rates (Boyle et al. 2020). Alternatively,
118 stronger precipitation or temperature seasonality may reduce bird diversity by reducing the
119 availability of food resources and imposing physiological constraints that reduce activity and

120 breeding (Williams and Middleton 2008; Karr 1976). Precipitation can generate both a linear
121 (Rahbek and Graves 2001) or unimodal effects on bird diversity (Freeman et al. 2024), while
122 temperature and precipitation seasonality can produce different responses (Quimbayo et al. 2024;
123 Keyser et al. 2024). However, it's not clear which climatic axis dominates (precipitation or
124 temperature) and what aspect (mean or seasonality) is the most important in shaping tropical bird
125 diversity in the lowlands and what is the prevalent response (shape) to these climatic factors.
126 Similarly, it is not well understood how the aggregated (total) abundance and biomass of bird
127 communities change along tropical lowland climatic gradients. Under the more-individuals
128 hypothesis it is expected that an increase in water availability, enhance both diversity and the
129 number of individuals (Storch et al. 2018; Evans et al. 2005; Currie et al. 2004). Similarly, it is
130 expected that biomass positively increased with both rainfall and temperature (Evans et al. 2005).
131 Stronger seasonality in rainfall has been shown to reduce tropical bird abundance and biomass in
132 Australian coastal forests (Williams and Middleton 2008). However, these hypotheses have rarely
133 been tested in other tropical regions, such as the Afrotropics, nor has their scale dependency.
134 The Congo Basin represents one of the least studied tropical regions. Central African rainforests
135 host unique bird communities (Fjeldsa 2020; Huntley and Voelker 2016). More than 1,000 bird
136 species are thought to occur in the region (Birdlife 2025; Jenkins et al. 2013; Jetz and Rahbek
137 2001). Nonetheless, few ecology research on bird communities was done at very local scales
138 (Brosset and Erard 1986; Waltert et al. 2005) highlighting the need for a quantitative
139 macroecological assessments of tropical bird communities in the Congo Basin. This region is
140 especially well suited for exploring bird communities responses to climate, as strong rainfall
141 gradients are associated with distinct floristic clusters (forests with different species composition)
142 (Droissart et al. 2018; Fayolle et al. 2014; Rejou-Mechain et al. 2021), and bird communities are
143 known to vary geographically across the basin (Chapin 1923), implying that there can be

144 variation in bird diversity and community structure associated with forests floristically and
145 structurally distinctive subject to different climatic regimes.

146 Studying the responses of tropical bird communities along regional environmental gradients
147 requires careful consideration of the spatial scale at which ecological patterns are assessed.

148 Spatial scale has long been recognized as a central issue in ecology (Levin 1992; Chase et al.
149 2018; Marsh and Ewers 2013; Rahbek 2005; Wiens 1989), yet its treatment has remained
150 problematic due to ambiguity in how scaling is defined and measured (Dungan et al. 2002; Wiens
151 1989) and the lack of sampling designs that explicitly allow community structure to be evaluated
152 across scales (Marsh and Ewers 2013; Simpson and Pearse 2021). Scale-dependent ecological
153 patterns may arise from changes in spatial grain, spatial extent, or their interaction (Chase et al.
154 2018; Dungan et al. 2002; Toews et al. 2017; Chase et al. 2019). However, cross-scale
155 comparisons are often confounded because increasing spatial extent typically involves
156 aggregating nested samples, such that smaller spatial scales constitute subsets of larger ones
157 (Scheiner et al. 2000; Dungan et al. 2002; Wiens 1989). As a result, observed scale dependence
158 may reflect changes in sampled area, species pools, or spatial heterogeneity rather than
159 underlying ecological processes. Fractal sampling designs offer a promising framework to
160 address these challenges by enabling comparisons across different levels of data aggregation
161 while holding spatial extent and basic sampling grain constant (Marsh and Ewers 2013; Simpson
162 and Pearse 2021). By varying the level of data aggregation—hereafter referred to as effective
163 spatial grain—such designs allow different amounts of community heterogeneity to be captured
164 within the same spatial extent, providing a controlled way to explore spatial scaling of
165 macroecological patterns. However, while fractal sampling designs have been used to investigate
166 spatial scaling, these approaches have largely emphasized spatial distance and sampling
167 configuration, rather than explicitly manipulating effective spatial grain (Marsh and Ewers 2013;

168 Simpson and Pearse 2021). This approach is particularly relevant for tropical bird communities,
169 which require sufficiently large sampled areas to capture the populations of coexisting species
170 and the heterogeneity in their spatial distribution (Brosset and Erard 1986; Martínez et al. 2023;
171 Robinson et al. 2000; 2021; Rutt et al. 2023; Terborgh et al. 1990). Hence, it remains unknown
172 how macroecological patterns and their climatic drivers vary across different effective spatial
173 grains in regional tropical gradients.

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Figure 1: Location of the four study sites along the southern–central Cameroon forest gradient (Campo Ma’an National Park, Dja Faunal Reserve, Lobéké National Park, and Mbam et Djerem National Park). White points inside each protected area showed the locations of the fractals. Elevation across the study region shows limited variation and remains consistently below 1,000 m a.s.l in all sampling points. The minimum distance among sites exceeds 300

km. Decadal variation in mean annual precipitation across study sites, illustrating long-term differences in rainfall regimes along the gradient using CHIRPS dataset.

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180 In addition to sampling designs that explicitly address spatial scaling, analytical frameworks that
181 provide a comprehensive characterization of community properties are essential for
182 macroecological inference. Hill numbers offer a unified framework for quantifying diversity
183 across orders of sensitivity to rare and dominant species, enabling consistent comparisons of
184 richness, evenness, and dominance across spatial scales (Chao et al., 2014; Hill, 1973; Chao and
185 Jost 2012). However, diversity metrics alone may mask changes in community organization.
186 Recent advances have therefore emphasized metrics that capture structural reorganization of
187 communities across spatial and temporal scales (Avolio et al. 2019). Together, these
188 complementary frameworks allow scale-dependent patterns in diversity and community structure
189 to be evaluated in an integrated manner.

190 Here, we present a multi-scale macroecological assessment of tropical forest bird communities
191 along a regional rainfall gradient in Cameroon, Central Africa. In the first part of the study, we
192 use a novel hybrid nested fractal sampling design to characterize bird diversity and community
193 structure across four forest sites and four sampling scenarios, three of which explicitly
194 manipulate effective spatial grain (Figures 2 and 3). In the second part, we examine climate–
195 community structure relationships by testing the effects of mean annual precipitation and
196 temperature, as well as their seasonal variability, on bird diversity and community structure, and
197 by evaluating how these relationships depend on spatial scale (Figure 3). Specifically, we expect
198 diversity, abundance and biomass to increase with precipitation and temperature, as predicted by
199 the climate hypothesis. We further test whether precipitation and temperature seasonality exert

200 stronger effects than mean climatic conditions, reflecting constraints imposed by temporal
201 resource availability and physiological limits. Finally, we assess how the magnitude and direction
202 of these climate–diversity relationships change across sampling scenarios, using effective spatial
203 grain as a scaling framework.

204 **Methods**

205 Study area & climatic gradient

206
207 Our study was conducted in the Republic of Cameroon, a Central African country between
208 approximately 2°N and 13°N latitude and 8°E and 16°E longitude (Figure 1). We focused on a
209 large environmental gradient of West and Central Africa (Conway et al. 2009; Washington et al.
210 2013). This gradient is characterized by a gradual decrease in rainfall from the coast towards the
211 interior and north, driven by complex wind patterns over the Atlantic Ocean (Washington et al.
212 2013), the geology and topography of the African plateau (e.g., domes; Akinsanola et al. 2025;
213 Jung et al. 2016), and the macroclimatic influence of the Sahara Desert (Cook 1997).
214 For this study, we focused only on a section of the gradient in Cameroon that encompasses
215 different forest types representing a precipitation gradient (Figures 1 and 2). We concentrated
216 only on the forested portion of the gradient, excluding savanna ecosystems and forest–savanna
217 ecotones, to examine diversity changes within a single biome, i.e. the Congolian rainforest.

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221 Characterization of rainfall and temperature regimes

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223 To test our hypotheses, we extracted broad-scale, high-resolution climatic data for the gradient
224 from four independent sources and used them to reconstruct the regional rainfall gradient
225 (Appendix S1, Figure S1 and Table S1). We combined multiple climatic datasets because the
226 climatology of Central Africa is particularly difficult to reconstruct accurately, largely due to the
227 limited number of weather stations. Several authors have recommended using multiple climatic
228 models to mitigate this limitation (Akinsanola et al. 2025; Washington et al. 2013).

229 First, we used the WORLDCLIM v2.0 database (Fick and Hijmans 2017), which compiles global
230 climatic data at 30 arc seconds spatial resolution and is a thin-plate spline interpolation product.
231 From this dataset, we extracted four bioclimatic variables for the period 1970–2000: mean annual
232 precipitation (MAP, BIO12), mean annual temperature (MAT, BIO1), temperature seasonality
233 (TS, BIO4), and precipitation seasonality (PS, BIO15).

234 Second, we used the CHELSA-BIOCLIM dataset which is an interpolated/downscaled climatic
235 product with a 30 arc seconds spatial resolution (Brun et al. 2022; Karger et al. 2017), from
236 which we extracted MAP and MAT values for our plots for the period 1981–2021.

237 Third, we obtained data from CHIRPS with 180 arc-seconds of resolution (Climate Hazards
238 Group InfraRed Precipitation with Stations) which combines satellite infrared with station data
239 using quasi-interpolation (Funk et al. 2015). We extracted monthly precipitation values from
240 1981 to 2025 and aggregated them to estimate annual precipitation per plot. These annual values
241 were then averaged to estimate MAP for each plot across 1981–2025.

242 Finally, we used the Climatic Research Unit (CRU) dataset (CRU) (Harris et al. 2020), which
243 provides climatic data based on meteorological records from 1901 to 2021 with 1800 arc-seconds
244 of resolution. We extracted monthly precipitation values from 1981 to 2021, aggregated them to

245 annual values per plot, and then calculated MAP for the last decade (2011–2021). Climatic
246 values from all datasets were extracted from raster files using the *terra* package in R, based on
247 the geographic coordinates of our alpha plots collected in the field with a Garmin GPSMAP 64s.
248 MAT values were consistent across datasets (Appendix S1, Table S1). For MAP, we used the
249 mean across datasets to obtain a single overall MAP value per plot, which we then used in
250 subsequent models. We used values of PS and TS only from WORLDCLIM because of the fine
251 grain resolution.

252 We take a long term perspective for bird community assembly (Ricklefs 2004; Wiens 1989; Price
253 et al. 2014) in the present work considering that the species pools for each part of the gradient
254 (forest sites) have been shaped by long term climatic conditions rather than only short term
255 changes. Therefore, we consider together climatic values for the last decades to influence
256 community diversity and structure rather than only short-term climatic variability. This is
257 supported by Work of (Brosset and Erard 1986) who found that old-growth forest bird
258 communities in Gabon remain relatively stable (in equilibrium) for several decades due to low
259 adult mortality rates (Erard 1987). Similar long-term stability has been found in amazonian
260 lowland bird communities (Martínez et al. 2023).

261 Site selection and sampling stratification

262
263 To sample bird communities, we implemented a stratified sampling design at the gradient level,
264 using the different floristic clusters associated with rainfall regimes as strata where the different
265 forest sites are located (Figures 1-3). Because the gradient covers a vast area and is shaped by
266 high environmental complexity—and because most forest areas are also degraded by
267 urbanization, roads, logging, and fragmentation (Minnemeyer and Bikié 2000; Panlasigui et al.
268 2018), we restricted sampling to old-growth forests located inside national parks. These sites

269 represent the main floristic clusters (primary lowland rain forest tree communities with different
270 taxonomic and functional composition) (Rejou-Mechain et al. 2021) (Figures 1 and 2).

271 We randomly allocated the start plot of each fractal within a predefined grid cell inside extensive
272 tracts of primary lowland tropical rainforest. All sites were located more than 30 km from the
273 nearest town, which is a widely used proxy for low human disturbance in the Congo Basin
274 (Grantham et al. 2020; Rejou-Mechain et al. 2021). Logging inside these protected areas is
275 minimal and we allocated the fractals in areas previously known to have not been logged based
276 on consultation with local communities and expert knowledge. There are no reports of exotic
277 plant or animal species in these forests.

278 We avoided habitats such as secondary forests, forest edges, *bais* (savanna clearings), as well as
279 azonal vegetation (aquatic systems, riparian zones). Restricting our plot network to primary
280 lowland rain forest allowed us to isolate the effects of climate and habitat on rainforest bird
281 communities by avoiding the confounding influences of land use on diversity patterns (Barlow et
282 al. 2016; Newbold et al. 2015). The only anthropogenic factor we could not fully account for was
283 poaching of large mammals, which remains widespread across Central Africa even inside
284 protected areas (Maisels et al. 2013). However, its impact on birds is less important than habitat
285 loss and degradation, which have much stronger effects on tropical bird diversity (Sodhi et al.
286 2010).

287 We stratified precipitation gradient in the following manner:

- 288 1. Very wet stratum (Campo Ma'an NP): 2500–3200 mm rainfall. Atlantic coastal tropical
289 lowland rainforest (Rejou-Mechain et al. 2021). Plots were located in moderately flat
290 terrain in the central protected area.

- 291 2. Wet and highly seasonal stratum (Mbam et Djerem NP): 1800–2000 mm rainfall.
292 Transitional tropical lowland rain forests on the northern edge of the basin, with stronger
293 seasonality and proximity to the Sudano-woodland savanna biome.
- 294 3. Intermediate stratum (Dja Faunal Reserve): 1600–1800 mm rainfall. Tropical lowland
295 forests located ~400 km inland from the Atlantic coast, in flat terrain associated with the
296 Dja River floodplain, though plots were >20 km away from the river.
- 297 4. Dry stratum (Lobeke NP): 1500–1600 mm rainfall. Tropical lowland forests ~700 km
298 inland, closer to the Congo Basin, with lower rainfall than Campo Ma’an and Dja.

299

300 Our stratified design ensured representation of both extremes of the rainfall gradient (Campo
301 Ma’an and Lobeke) and intermediate points (Dja, Mbam et Djerem). Such coverage of the full
302 environmental range—here restricted to the rainforest biome—is essential in gradient studies
303 (Guo et al. 2023).

304 Fractal sampling design and effective spatial grain for sampling communities in environmental
305 gradients:

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307 To study bird communities across the different forest sites in the gradient, we implemented a
308 novel hybrid fractal sampling design that allows us to explore macroecological patterns in four
309 spatial contexts (sampling scenarios) (Figures 2 and 3). Our design was inspired by previous
310 fractal approaches based on geometric structures (Marsh and Ewers 2013; Simpson and Pearse
311 2021). We retained the core principle of equilateral triangles (Simpson and Pearse 2021), adding
312 new sampling units to i) sample more populations in the central areas of the fractals, ii) targeting
313 rare species with small home-ranges and iii) sample additional environmental variation that can
314 occur in the center of the fractals .

315 Spatial extent, defined as the total geographic area encompassed by the sampling units (Wiens
316 1989), was held constant across all sites. This extent corresponds to a large equilateral triangle
317 with side lengths of 2,700 m, covering approximately 3.16 km² (Figure 2, Table 1). The basic
318 spatial grain, defined as the area of the smallest sampling units (Wiens 1989; Turner 1990), was
319 also kept constant and corresponds to individual point counts with a 100 m radius (\approx 3.14 ha).
320 The parameter manipulated across sampling scenarios was effective spatial grain, which
321 represents the emergent spatial resolution at which community properties are quantified as a
322 result of aggregating sampling units within a fixed spatial extent (Wiens 1989). In our study,
323 effective spatial grain therefore defines the scale of inference for diversity and community
324 structure. We use the term *effective spatial grain* rather than *grain size* because the latter has been
325 used inconsistently in the literature to refer to multiple and sometimes overlapping aspects of
326 spatial scale (Wiens 1989; Dungan et al. 2002).

327 Replicating this sampling design across four sites along the regional rainfall gradient allows us to
328 examine spatial scaling through changes in effective spatial grain while holding constant spatial
329 extent as well as basic spatial grain. This design enables a direct evaluation of how effective
330 spatial grain *per se* influences the detection of macroecological patterns and the testing of
331 ecological theories.

332 In each study site (Campo Ma'an, Dja, Lobeke, and Mbam et Djerem), we established a
333 replicated hybrid nested fractal sampling design to investigate bird community diversity and
334 structure across spatial scales (Figure 2). Below, we describe the four sampling scenarios derived
335 from this design and summarized in Table 1

- 336 1. Full sampling context: The full sampling scenario consisted of 36 point-count plots per
337 site, arranged in four clusters: three equilateral triangles (10 plots each) and one central

338 hexagon (6 plots) located between the triangles. Together, these plots covered 35.7% of
339 the total spatial extent (Figure 2), corresponding to an effective spatial grain of 113 ha.
340 Distances between neighboring plots within clusters were 300 m, following benchmark
341 recommendations for systematic point-count spacing (Robinson and Curtis 2020). This
342 configuration concentrates sampling effort both centrally and within nested substructures,
343 providing the maximum statistical power in our study. Across all sites, this scenario
344 represents the full sampling intensity of the regional gradient (n = 144 plots).

- 345
- 346 2. Third triad sampling scenario: In the third triad scenario, we excluded the central hexagon
347 and associated central plots, resulting in 27 plots per site arranged in three equilateral
348 triangles. This configuration covered 26.85% of the total extent (Figure 2) and yielded an
349 effective spatial grain of 84 ha. Distances between neighboring plots within clusters
350 remained 300 m, while distances between clusters increased to 900 m. Compared with the
351 full sampling scenario, this design shifts statistical power toward the periphery of the
352 sampling area, while maintaining substantial spatial replication
- 353
- 354 3. Second triad sampling scenario: The second triad scenario retained only plots separated
355 by 900 m, resulting in 9 plots per site and covering 8.95% of the total spatial extent
356 (Figure 2). The corresponding effective spatial grain was 28 ha. In this scenario, both the
357 central hexagon and inner plots were excluded, leading to reduced statistical power within
358 clusters and at the extremes relative to the previous scenarios, while increasing the mean
359 inter-plot distance.
- 360 4. First triad sampling scenario: The first triad scenario included only plots separated by
361 2,700 m, resulting in 3 plots per site and covering 2.98% of the total spatial extent (Figure

362 2). This configuration corresponds to an effective spatial grain of 9 ha. This scenario
363 represents the coarsest scale of inference, characterized by the largest spatial distances
364 among plots and a strong reduction in sampling intensity and statistical power.

365
366 To facilitate interpretation of the fractal sampling design, we introduce a consistent nomenclature
367 for its main structural elements, explicitly inspired by the classical α - β - γ diversity framework of
368 Whittaker (Whittaker 1960). Importantly, this nomenclature refers to *sampling units* and *spatial*
369 *organization*, rather than to diversity metrics themselves.

370 The basic sampling units of the study are termed α points, reflecting that each point count (plot)
371 samples a very local area within the spatial domain of inference (spatial extent) of each site
372 (Figure 2). Groups of point counts arranged in equilateral triangular or hexagonal configurations
373 are termed β clusters, as they are designed to capture spatial turnover among α points and among
374 clusters, thereby representing the spatial component associated with β diversity (Figure 2).

375 The complete set of α points sampled within a site is referred to as the γ fractal, representing the
376 full sampling structure used to characterize community diversity within the site's spatial domain
377 of inference (Figure 2). γ fractals are conceived as standardized sampling units that draw samples
378 from the regional species pool along the environmental gradient, without implying exhaustive
379 coverage or approximation of the entire regional pool.

380 This nomenclature provides a coherent link between sampling design and classical diversity
381 concepts, and facilitates targeted analyses of α -, β -, and γ -level patterns by focusing on specific
382 structural elements of the design according to the research question and hypothesis.

383 For clarity, this nomenclature is introduced to aid interpretation of the sampling design and is
384 used selectively throughout the manuscript, while most analyses are described using neutral terms
385 (e.g., plots, clusters, sites) to avoid confusion with diversity metrics.

386 Bird sampling

387 *Point counts*

388 We sampled bird communities using point counts (corresponding to the alpha points) regularly
389 located at the center of each plot (Figure 2). Each point count was surveyed for 10 minutes
390 between 5:45 a.m. and midday. To minimize bias related to time of arrival, the starting point and
391 direction of surveys were rotated daily (Blake 1992; Robinson and Curtis 2020). We used a
392 radius of 100 meters for each point count to allow freedom to the ornithologist to include any
393 species heard or seen (Robinson and Curtis 2020). Because the distance was always 300 meters,
394 over-counting is very improbable (Buckland et al. 2008; Ralph et al. 1995) even for wide ranging
395 birds (Marsden 1999). Each point was surveyed six times, yielding 216-point counts per gradient
396 site, except for two points in Campo Mann (alpha 10), which were visited only five times due to
397 high elephant activity. We performed 10-point counts per day in one of the clusters of the fractal.
398 In total, 862-point counts were completed across the gradient. Temporal replication was designed
399 to increase the probability of detecting rare, quiet, or cryptic species (Mackenzie and Royle 2005;
400 Robinson and Curtis 2020).

401 Within each point count we registered the species identity, distance to the observer and the
402 number of individuals per species. At each point count, we recorded species identity, number of
403 individuals per species, and distance to the observer. Surveys were not conducted during rainfall
404 or when raindrops interfered with detection (Robinson & Curtis, 2020). We excluded nocturnal
405 birds and raptors flying high over the canopy, but we included forest raptors because they are a
406 core element of these communities (Erad and Brosset 1986). All counts were performed by FNM,
407 a senior field ornithologist with over 20 years of experience identifying Cameroonian birds. This
408 expertise ensured reliable sampling and reduced observer bias—an essential requirement in
409 diverse tropical forests (Karr 1981; Robinson et al. 2018; Terborgh et al. 1990). Individuals that

410 could not be identified to species (<0.01% of records) were assigned to genus. All surveys were
411 also audio recorded (Zoom H4n Pro at Campo Ma'an; Sound Mix Device II Pro with a 2085
412 Sennheiser omnidirectional microphone at other sites), providing vouchers for subsequent
413 taxonomic identification (Robinson and Curtis 2020).

414 Through the study we followed the taxonomy of Clements /ebird (Clements 2025) for our species
415 lists. While other taxonomic lists exist, we pragmatically used this one, without the necessity to
416 imply we agree with all the taxonomic treatments.

417 Sampling spanned two years (2023–2024) (see Appendix S1 Table S2). Our effort was
418 maximized during the dry season, when breeding activity peaks and vocalizations are most
419 frequent. However, we also covered the transitions to the wet season. This timing ensured the
420 highest detectability of species, especially for species that are rare or cryptic. Our choice of dry-
421 season sampling is consistent with empirical studies in Central Africa, which show that most
422 vocal activity associated with breeding occurs during this period (Brosset and Erard 1986; Serle
423 1981; Vokurková et al. 2018).

424 Phase I: Characterizing patterns of Gamma diversity and community structure

425
426 The first phase of our study focused on uncovering macroecological patterns of gamma diversity
427 (site-level diversity) and community structure across the different sampling scenarios using a
428 combination of analytical frameworks (Figure 3), which we describe below.

429 *Hill numbers*

430 To characterize patterns of site-level diversity (Gamma), we used the Hill numbers framework
431 (Chao et al. 2014). Hill numbers express diversity through indices that weight species abundances
432 differently. When abundances are not considered, all species are treated equally, representing

433 observed (raw) species richness ($q = 0$) which makes it more sensitive to rare species. When
434 species are weighted by their abundances, common species contribute more ($q = 1$, the Hill-
435 Shannon diversity, whereas weighting strongly toward the most abundant species emphasizes
436 dominance ($q = 2$, Hill-Simpson diversity) (Chao et al. 2014). Therefore, they represent the
437 effective number of species, which facilitates comparison across sites. Although the linearization
438 of diversity indices has generated some debate (Ricotta and Feoli 2024), Hill numbers remain a
439 robust framework for comparing diversity, particularly in highly diverse tropical communities
440 where many species are rare (Ausprey et al. 2023; Chao and Jost 2012; Chazdon et al. 2022).
441 Because each plot was surveyed with six temporal replicates, was separated by at least 300 m
442 (Figure 2), and was conducted by the same experienced observer (FNM) in homogeneous forest
443 habitat, we used abundance-based data (raw counts) to estimate Hill numbers instead of incidence
444 data. Abundance data are appropriate for Hill number estimation when temporal replication is
445 available (Ausprey et al. 2023; Martínez et al. 2023), and raw data are especially useful when
446 distance sampling models cannot be fitted reliably for most species (Banks-Leite et al. 2014;
447 Sedláček et al. 2023), as in our case (see section Aggregated community abundance and biomass
448). Posterior abundance estimates represent latent states conditional on model assumptions and
449 uncertainty, combining them with raw observed counts would violate principles of coherent
450 statistical inference by mixing observational data with model-derived quantities and failing to
451 propagate uncertainty (Hooten and Hobbs 2015; Kéry and Royle 2016). Therefore, we used
452 abundance raw data for estimating the hill numbers. Species abundance raw data per point count
453 was estimated as the maximum number of individuals detected across the six replicates (Betts et
454 al. 2005; Cox et al. 2018; Gaüzère et al. 2015; Jankowski et al. 2009; Ralph et al. 1995). This
455 measure is more conservative but less subject to bias (especially overestimation) than other
456 measures (Rigby and Johnson 2025).

457 *Characterizing patterns of gamma diversity*

458 To compare gamma diversity among forest sites (our reference assemblages) (Chao and Jost
459 2012; Chao et al. 2014) , we pooled all abundance data at the site level (gamma fractal) and
460 calculated Hill numbers ($q = 0, 1, 2$) using the R package iNEXT.3D (Chao et al. 2021).
461 Following (Chao et al. 2020), we produced four complementary types of diversity profiles for the
462 full sampling scenario: (1) abundance-based rarefaction–extrapolation curves, (2) sample
463 coverage curves, (3) asymptotic versus observed diversity profiles, and (4) evenness profiles.
464 Together, these profiles provide a comprehensive assessment of diversity patterns among
465 communities (Chao et al. 2020).
466 For coverage-based rarefaction/extrapolation curves and to assess sample completeness,
467 additionally to the estimators implemented in iNEXT.3D, we used the abundance-based sample
468 coverage estimator derived from Good–Turing frequency formulas (Appendix S2, Figure S1)
469 which explicitly accounts for non-random sampling and spatial aggregation of individuals and
470 overcomes the limitations of incidence-based estimators when applied to abundance data (Chiu
471 2023). We compared the derived sample coverage from both estimators.
472 To compare gamma diversity across sampling scenarios, we subset the point-count data
473 according to each scenario (see Fractal design section, Figure 2) and conduct independent
474 iNEXT.3D analyses for each sampling scenario (third, second, and first triads). For each
475 scenario, we generated the same set of Hill-number profiles as for the full sampling scenario and
476 compared sites under these scenarios.

477 *Community structural reorganization across sampling scenarios*

478 To explore the degree of reorganization in community structure across sampling scenarios at the
479 site level (gamma fractal) we applied the framework proposed by (Avolio et al. (2019). This

480 framework allows tracking spatial or temporal changes in evenness, species identity, and
481 abundance rankings through RAC metrics. Specifically, we calculated: (1) ΔP (Delta P), the
482 proportional change in species' relative abundances across space or time; (2) Δ Evenness which
483 measures changes in the distribution of abundances among species; (3) Δ Rank, which quantify
484 the extent to which species change positions in the rank–abundance distribution; and (4) Δ
485 Species difference, which reflects species gains or losses between communities. We calculated
486 these metrics for transitions between sampling scenarios: (i) full sampling to third triad scenario,
487 (ii) third triad scenario to second triad scenario, and (iii) second triad scenario to first triad
488 scenario. All RAC metrics were computed using the codyn package (Hallett et al. 2016).

489 *Fitting SADs models across sampling scenarios*

490 To characterize the prevailing statistical structure of species abundances across sampling
491 scenarios at the site level (gamma fractal), we fitted species–abundance distribution (SAD)
492 models to the four different sampling scenarios. We compared the performance of three widely
493 used SAD models —the log-series (Fisher et al. 1943), the Poisson lognormal (Preston 1948)—
494 using Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC) and its small-sample correction (AICc) and negative
495 binomial. For each sampling scenario, the model with the lowest AIC/AICc value was considered
496 the best-supported distribution. All models were fitted using maximum likelihood methods
497 implemented in the *sads* R package (Prado and Chalom 2024). Because Hill numbers summarize
498 diversity without assuming a specific abundance distribution, SAD model fitting was used here
499 solely as a complementary diagnostic of community structure.

500

501

502 Phase II: Testing the climate theory

503

504 During the second phase of the study, we focused on exploring the predictions of the climate
505 hypothesis at the level of the point counts (Alpha points) across different sampling scenarios
506 (Figure 3). Next, we describe the details for this assessment of the climate theory.

507 *Assessing alpha diversity change across the gradient*

508 For alpha diversity (point-count level, alpha points in our sampling scheme), we estimated size-
509 standardized Hill numbers ($q = 0, 1, 2$) using iNEXT under the rarefaction/extrapolation
510 framework of (Chao et al. 2014). Diversity estimates were extracted at the maximum common
511 number of individuals across point counts and used as response variables in subsequent models
512 for hypothesis testing. Size-based and coverage-based Hill-number estimates were highly
513 correlated across point counts (Pearson $r = 0.97$; Spearman $r = 0.97$ for $q = 0$), indicating that
514 results are robust to the choice of standardization (Appendix S2, Table S2).

515 Although sample coverage is generally the preferred basis for standardizing diversity
516 comparisons (Chao et al. 2014; Chao and Jost 2012; Chiu 2023; Roswell et al. 2021), coverage at
517 the point-count level was low and highly heterogeneous (Appendix S2, Table S1). Standardizing
518 all point counts to a common coverage level ($\approx 30\text{--}40\%$) would therefore require rarefaction to
519 very small sample sizes, resulting in substantial information loss and limited inference.
520 Moreover, coverage-based standardization is not recommended when individual samples do not
521 adequately represent the reference assemblage (Chao and Jost 2012; Chao et al. 2014), which in
522 our study is better approximated at the aggregated site level. For these reasons, we did not use
523 coverage-based or asymptotic Hill numbers at the point-count level, given the high uncertainty of
524 such estimates under low coverage (Roswell et al. 2021).

Figure 3: Two-phase analytical workflow linking macroecological patterns and climate hypotheses across a lowland precipitation gradient. The upper panel summarizes the two phases of the study. Phase 1 (γ -scale) characterizes site-level macroecological patterns (γ -fractals), including gamma diversity, species abundance distributions (SADs), and rank–abundance metrics. Phase 2 (α -scale) tests climate hypotheses at the point-count level (α points nested within β clusters and study sites). For Hypotheses 1–3, black lines indicate linear expectations derived from classical climate–diversity theory, whereas blue curves illustrate alternative nonlinear (asymptotic) responses; other potential forms (e.g., unimodal or declining relationships) are omitted for clarity. Hypothesis 4 illustrates the joint effects of mean annual precipitation and precipitation seasonality, with a schematic comparison of their relative importance. The lower panel shows the forest sites along the climatic gradient; small fractal icons indicate deployment of the full sampling scenario at each site (36 α plots per site). Full details of the fractal sampling design are provided in Figure 2.

526 *Aggregated community abundance and biomass*

527

528 For abundance and biomass, we calculated aggregated measures that reflect the total number of
529 individuals and total energy in each point count (alpha point). We defined aggregated community
530 abundance (ACA) as the sum of the abundances of all species in a point count, representing
531 community size in terms of individuals (Srivastava and Lawton 1998). Similarly, aggregated
532 community biomass (ACB) was defined as the sum of the biomass of all species in a point count,
533 representing the total energy in the local community (Harte 2011; Lindeman 1942).

534 ACA was calculated as the sum of the maximum raw abundances of all species detected in a
535 point count across temporal replicates. ACB was then derived by multiplying raw species
536 abundance by average body weight and summing across all species in a plot (Holmes and Sturges
537 1975; Wiens and Innis 1974). Species body mass data were obtained from AVONET (Tobias et
538 al. 2022).

539 Imperfect detection is an important consideration when estimating species-specific abundance.
540 Accordingly, we fitted multispecies hierarchical distance sampling (HDS) models separately for
541 each site (Campo Ma'an, Dja, Lobeke, and Mbam et Djerem) using the *msDS* function in the
542 *spAbundance* package (Doser et al. 2024). However, due to the low number of detections for
543 most species, reliable HDS models could be fitted for only a small subset (29%) of the
544 community at each site, as commonly observed in species-rich tropical bird assemblages
545 (Buckland et al. 2008; Banks-Leite et al. 2014).

546 Although community-level models can, in some cases, borrow information across species to
547 estimate abundance for rare taxa, such approaches implicitly assume that detection processes are
548 sufficiently similar among species (Gilbert et al. 2024; Sollmann et al. 2016; Zipkin et al. 2023),
549 for tropical forest birds, this assumption is problematic because species differ markedly in life

550 history, foraging strategy, vocal behavior, and social organization (Brosset and Erard 1986; Karr
551 1981; Terborgh et al. 1990). Consequently, assuming shared detection functions—or predicting
552 them from traits—can introduce substantial bias (Kéry and Royle 2016; Sollmann et al. 2016).
553 For these reasons, and because our objective in this study is to assess community-level patterns
554 rather than species-specific abundances, we did not incorporate HDS-derived abundance
555 estimates into our abundance models or Hill-number analyses. While this approach may
556 underestimate the true abundance of some common species, the high sample coverage achieved
557 at the site level indicates that most individuals present in the community were likely detected.
558 Thus, raw abundance values provide a consistent and robust basis for community-level inference
559 across sites and spatial scales.

560

561 *Statistical analyses*

562

563 For the second phase of our study, we applied different statistical models to test our hypotheses
564 according to the response variable, following a two-parts modelling framework. In the first part
565 of hypothesis testing (Hypothesis 1-3), single-covariate models were used to describe diversity–
566 climate relationships along individual environmental gradients. In the second part (Hypothesis 4),
567 nested models were used to test the relative importance of climatic axes after accounting for
568 covariation among predictors.

569 We fitted single-covariate models to explicitly test the effects of individual climatic variables on
570 alpha diversity (Hill numbers $q = 0, 1, \text{ and } 2$), aggregated community abundance (ACA), and
571 aggregated community biomass (ACB) (Part one). Gamma diversity was quantified using Hill-
572 number profiles and compared descriptively among sites due to limited site-level replication.

573 The aim of the first phase was to test a well-established ecological hypothesis, namely the climate
574 hypothesis (Currie et al. 2004; Wright 1983; Evans et al. 2005). Accordingly, we used single-
575 covariate models for parameter inference (Tredennick et al. 2021) within the domain of inference
576 defined by our sampling locations. Focusing on a single climatic predictor at a time minimizes
577 confounding and avoids biases associated with model selection and multicollinearity, which can
578 complicate inference when predictors covary (Berk et al. 2010; Graham 2003; Dormann et al.
579 2013; Whittingham et al. 2006; Kuchibhotla et al. 2022; Tredennick et al. 2021; Yates et al.
580 2023). This phase therefore provided interpretable estimates of the marginal effects of individual
581 climatic variables on response variables, without conditioning on other correlated predictors
582 For this phase, we fitted models with one climatic covariate (e.g., mean annual precipitation,
583 MAP) and one response variable (e.g., hill diversity at $q = 0$) at the four different sampling
584 scenarios. Models used MAP and MAT averaged across the four climatic products, whereas PS
585 and TS were obtained from WorldClim only.

586 For each model, we followed a standardized protocol (Zuur et al. 2010) where we 1) transform the
587 response variable to allow meaningful comparisons, 2) include random intercepts, 3) select the
588 appropriate model type based on residual distributions, 4) evaluating whether relationships were
589 linear or nonlinear, 5) validating models by checking assumptions (normality, heteroscedasticity)
590 and diagnosing issues (residual patterns, outliers, overdispersion).

591 Model diagnostics were performed using the performance package (Lüdecke et al. 2021) and
592 DHARMA (Hartig et al. 2024). We created detailed reports for each model (Appendix S5).

593 Models that met assumptions were retained for inference; otherwise, we fitted alternative
594 specifications (e.g., quadratic terms, GAMs, negative binomial for abundance, gamma for
595 biomass) to ensure valid inference. Because we compared climatic covariates of the same axis

596 (e.g., MAT and TS) in the nested models, we did not incorporate interactions in single covariate
597 models.

598 For all models, we included two random intercepts to account for the hierarchical sampling
599 design: one for gradient strata (site) and another for clusters (beta clusters). Because we used a
600 single diversity value per alpha plot (point count), we did not include a random intercept at that
601 level. Since all alpha plots (point counts) contained multiple species records, zero inflation was
602 not an issue

603 In the second part of the data analysis, we implemented nested mixed-effects models including
604 pairs of related climatic covariates. The aim remained parameter inference, but now focused on
605 testing the combined effects of precipitation variables (mean annual precipitation, MAP, and
606 precipitation seasonality, PS) and temperature variables (mean annual temperature, MAT, and
607 temperature seasonality, TS) on the different response variables, while accounting for covariation
608 among predictors.

609 Climatic predictors were not combined into a single nested model because precipitation- and
610 temperature-related variables showed strong cross-domain correlations, potentially obscuring
611 their individual effects. However, collinearity within each climatic domain was low (MAP–PS:
612 VIF = 0.41; MAT–TS: VIF = 0.21; Appendix S5 Figure S1), with all VIF values far below
613 thresholds indicating problematic multicollinearity (Dormann et al. 2013).

614 Specifically, we assessed whether nested models including both covariates more parsimoniously
615 explained community structure compared to a null (intercept-only) model. These models also
616 allowed us to test whether mean climate values or temporal variance (seasonality) had the
617 stronger influence on diversity, abundance, and biomass.

618 As in the first phase, we also evaluated model assumptions but used likelihood ratio tests to
619 evaluate whether the inclusion of climatic covariates significantly improved model fit. Nested
620 models were fitted for MAP + PS and separately for MAT + TS for the four sampling scenarios
621 To explore the direction and shape of climatic effects across the climatic gradient we used model
622 predictions from the single covariate models to generate trend plots with 95 % confidence
623 intervals (CIs). Predictions were restricted to the observed range of each climatic covariate across
624 the gradient.

625 To characterize how the influence of each climatic covariate on diversity, abundance and biomass
626 changes across sampling scenarios, we constructed plots showing model beta coefficients and
627 associated CIs.

628 Models were fitted using several R packages: *lme4* (Bates et al. 2015) for Gaussian, negative
629 binomial and quadratic mixed-effects models, *mgcv* and *gamm4* (Wood 2017; Wood and Scheipl
630 2025) for GAMs/GAMMs, and *broom.mixed* (Bolker et al. 2024) to extract model coefficients.

631 All analyses were conducted in R (R core team 2024). Complete R scripts and associated
632 functions used in the analyses will be archived in a public repository upon acceptance of the
633 manuscript

634 *Sensitivity analyses*

635 Implementing the fractal sampling design involves a trade-off in the number of locations where
636 gamma fractals can be replicated in forest sites. In addition, our analyses draw on multiple
637 climatic datasets that differ in spatial resolution, and the distances between alpha plots within the
638 same beta cluster within each forest location were relatively small (300 m). To ensure that our
639 results are robust to these potential sources of variation, we conducted a set of cross-validation

640 analyses. Specifically, we assessed the influence of (i) individual forest sites, (ii) alternative
641 climatic datasets, and (iii) spatial autocorrelation on our model outputs. These sensitivity tests
642 were performed using the full dataset ($n = 144$), which provides the maximum sampling intensity
643 we deployed across the gradient. By using the full dataset, model estimates are not confounded
644 by the exclusion of plots or the distances between them, unlike in the sampling scenarios for the
645 triads.

646 We did a LOSO (leave-one-site-out) sensitivity analysis (Roberts et al. 2017) that explored how
647 the removal of data of one gradient site (Campo Mann, Mbam et Djerem, Dja, Lobeke)
648 influenced our model estimates. We systematically removed data of the plots of one gradient site
649 (e.g., Lobeke) and assessed the slope, estimates and plotted to have an evaluation of site influence
650 per response variable. We also conducted a LODO (leave-one-dataset-out) sensitive analysis
651 (Roberts et al. 2017) where we explored the influence in our estimates of removing a specific
652 climatic dataset (wordclim, bioclim, CHIRPS and CRU) on model estimates.

653 To evaluate the influence of spatial autocorrelation (SAC) within and between gradient strata, we
654 computed Moran's I and correlograms for climatic predictors (rainfall, temperature, and their
655 seasonalities) and for model residuals (Dormann et al. 2007). Because the distance between plots
656 of different gradient sites was large (> 300 km), we expected minimal SAC among strata but
657 potential SAC within forest sites. To control for non-independence due to nested sampling, all
658 mixed models included random intercepts for site and beta-cluster, which absorb most spatial
659 dependencies.

660 In addition, we explicitly evaluated the potential influence of residual spatial structure on
661 parameter estimates by fitting spatially explicit models (Crane et al. 2012; Dormann et al. 2007)
662 that incorporated spatial smooths of geographic coordinates (longitude, latitude) using

663 generalized additive models (GAMs) and comparing these to non-spatial models. This two-step
664 approach allowed us to determine whether the detected climatic effects were robust to spatial
665 autocorrelation and to quantify how much of the climatic signal was spatially structured across
666 the regional gradients.

667 **Results**

668 Across all sites, we recorded 10589 detections representing 175 species (15 orders, 42 families,
669 106 genera). Observed gamma diversity was highest in Mbam et Djerem (123 species) and lowest
670 in Campo Ma'an (107 species; Table 2). Turnover was relatively low at higher taxonomic levels,
671 with 66% of orders, 76% of families, and 55% of genera shared across all sites, but substantially
672 higher at the species level, where only 68 species (38%) were recorded at all sites (Appendix S1,
673 Figure S3).

674 Species richness was dominated by Bulbuls (Pycnonotidae), Flycatchers (Muscicapidae),
675 Cuckoos (Cuculidae), Barbets (Lybiidae), Hornbills (Bucerotidae), Cisticolas (Cisticolidae) and
676 Sunbirds (Nectariniidae). These seven families represent 16% of the total families, but account
677 for 41% of the total species (Appendix S1, Figure S2). The most frequently detected species were
678 mainly understory insectivorous oscine passerines, such as the Greenbills (*Eurillas virens* and *E.*
679 *latirostris*), the Sunbird (*Cyanomitra olivacea*) and a Barbet (*Pogoniulus subsulphureus*) together
680 with one large hornbill (*Ceratogymna atrata*). These species each had > 300 detections across all
681 sites (Appendix S1 Figure S4). The majority of detections (75%) occurred within 50 m radius
682 (Appendix S1 Table S5). Most detections were auditory (94%), with only 4% visual (Appendix
683 S1 Table S6).

684 At 100 ha (full sampling scenario), total raw abundance—calculated as the sum of species-level
685 maximum counts per point count—was comparable across sites, ranging from 1,624 in Campo
686 Ma'an to 1,982 in Lobéké (Appendix S1, Table S7).

687 Sample-size and coverage-based rarefaction curves both showed high completeness across forest
688 sites, with sampling of common and dominant species ($q=1$ and $q=2$) more complete than
689 sampling of rare species (Figure 4). Sample coverage increased from ~75% in the first triad
690 scenario to >99% in the full sampling scenario (Appendix S2, Figures S2-S5).

691 Across all forest sites, sample completeness curves suggested that 1000 individuals were
692 sufficient to capture full coverage with the full sampling scenario (Appendix S2 Figure S6-S9).

693 Using the adjusted estimator for abundance-based sample coverage showed the same high
694 coverage (97-99%) across the sites with 36-point counts (Appendix S2 Figure S1).

695 Observed versus asymptotic diversity profiles showed that common and dominant species were
696 almost fully sampled, whereas rare species were still well represented. Asymptotic curves suggest
697 additional undetected species, as expected in tropical forests (Appendix S2, Figures S10-S13).

698 We considered that a very small fraction of undetected species across all the forest sites were the
699 same set of extremely rare canopy foragers and aerial feeders flying over canopy, or species
700 present locally with highly specific habitat preferences (e.g., Gray-necked Rockfowl for rocky
701 areas *Picathartes oreas*, Dja River Swamp Warbler *Bradypterus grandis* for tickets inside bais),
702 not present per se inside our sampling points. Rare species remained underrepresented in the
703 sampling scenarios with smaller triads and at the first triad scenario all diversity was
704 undersampled (Appendix S2, Figures S10-S13).

705

706

707 Patterns of Gamma diversity in the gradient

708

709 In the full sampling scenario (n=144) and maximum coverage (97-99%), richness (q=0) peaked
710 in the wet and more seasonal forest site (Mbam et Djerem), while Shannon (q=1) and Simpson
711 (q=2) diversity were lowest in the driest location (Lobeke) (Figure 4). Coverage-based curves
712 confirmed that at the maximum coverage Mbam et Djerem bird communities showed higher
713 richness, Shannon and Simpson values than other strata, with small differences for richness but
714 stronger contrast for Shannon and Simpson (Appendix S2, Figure S2). At a reduced coverage
715 (levels 75% or 50%), Mbam et Djerem still retains the highest richness and diversity values
716 (Appendix S2, Figure S2), indicating that this transitional forest site consistently holds most
717 gamma diversity regardless of coverage.

718 Asymptotic diversity profiles further supported this pattern, showing that Mbam et Djerem had
719 the highest asymptotic gamma diversity across Hill numbers, while Lobeke had the lowest
720 (Appendix S2 Figure S10).

721 Gamma diversity patterns varied across sampling scenarios corresponding to different effective
722 spatial grains. At broader effective spatial grains (third triad scenario), the wettest site (Campo
723 Ma'an) exhibited the highest gamma diversity, whereas relative diversity rankings shifted at finer
724 effective spatial grains (second and first triad scenarios) (Appendix S2).

725 Evenness profiles also revealed shifts in evenness across the gradient and sampling scenarios.

726 The full sampling scenario revealed the wettest sites (Campo and Mbam et Djerem) had the
727 highest evenness, whereas Lobeke had the most uneven community structure (Figure 5). These
728 rankings consistently shifted across the different sampling scenarios (Appendix S2, Figures S17-
729 S19).

Figure 4: Sample-size-based rarefaction (solid lines) and extrapolation (dashed lines) curves of taxonomic Gamma diversity (Hill numbers $q = 0, 1,$ and 2) based on point-count data for four forest sites. Shaded areas represent 95% confidence intervals, and symbols indicate observed diversity at the reference sample size.

730

731 Community structure reorganization across sampling scenarios

732 Structural metrics confirmed stability of forest bird communities at the site level when compared

733 between the full sampling scenario and third triad scenario implying a small change in

734 community structure with small changes in effective spatial grain (Figure 6). However, large

735 changes in effective spatial grain (transitions between the third triad scenario and second triad

736 scenario) showed the largest changes for Δ evenness indicating a large restructuring of evenness

737 (Figure 6). Nevertheless, the shifts in evenness were not equal among forest sites (Figure 6).

738 Shifts in species dominance ranks (Δ Rank) were the largest in the transition between the second

739 triad scenario and first triad scenario, showing that relatively small changes in effective spatial

740 grain at fine resolution (from 24 ha to 9 ha) convey changes in the species that are the most
 741 abundant across the gradient (Figure 6).

742 Differences in species identity (ΔSp) also revealed shifts in transitions especially between the
 743 second triad scenario and first triad scenario, and more heterogeneity among forest sites in the
 744 transitions between the third triad scenario and second triad scenario (Figure 6).

745 Redistribution in species relative abundances (ΔP) peaked at the transition between the second
 746 triad scenario and first triad scenario (Figure 6).

Figure 5: Evenness profiles ($E_q = D_q / D_0$) based on Hill numbers ($q = 1$ and $q = 2$) for whole bird communities of the four forest sites (site level). Profiles highlight differences in dominance structure among assemblages, with lower evenness indicating stronger dominance by a few species.

747

748 SADs

749

750 Species abundance distributions (SADs) at the site level were generally best described by a

751 Poisson lognormal model across forest sites and sampling scenarios, except in Mbam et Djerem

752 where a log-series fitted best for the full sampling and third triad scenario (Appendix S2, Table

753 S3). Another exception was the Dja, where negative binomial was the best fit only for the first

754 triad scenario.

Figure 6: Metrics of community structural reorganization across transitions between sampling scenarios at the site level (γ -fractal). Panels A–D show changes in community structural metrics capturing reorganization of relative abundance and dominance patterns across sampling scenarios that modify effective spatial grain while holding spatial extent constant. Metrics summarize shifts in community structure associated with transitions from the full sampling scenario to reduced triad scenarios at the site (γ -fractal) level.

755

756

757 Hypothesis 1: Climate positively influences observed alpha diversity across spatial scales

758

759 Alpha diversity showed contrasting patterns across the gradient depending on the different facets
760 of alpha diversity assessed (Table 3). MAP did not significantly influence local species richness
761 ($q=0$), while it significantly influenced the diversity of common ($q=1$) and dominant species
762 ($q=2$) (Figure 7). The responses were unimodal showing a peak at intermediate levels of
763 precipitation (Figure 7). Mean annual precipitation showed weak and inconsistent relationships
764 with size-standardized Hill-number alpha diversity, with high uncertainty and no statistically
765 significant effects across sampling scenarios (Appendix S3, Figures S1). The effects of MAT on
766 alpha diversity were not significant with a small effect on species richness and inconsistent
767 effects for richness and Simpson across sampling scenarios (Appendix S3, Figures S2, S8).

768 In contrast, PS and TS significantly had effects on richness and alpha diversity showing
769 curvilinear and unimodal shapes respectively (Figure 7, Appendix S3, Figure S3 and S4). Across
770 sampling scenarios, the effects of PS were very consistent, whereas the effects of TS greatly
771 shifted (Figure 8, Appendix S3, Figure S3 and S4).

772

Figure 7: Model-based predictions of size-standardized Hill numbers for alpha diversity estimated at the point-count (α -point) level. Panels A–B show predicted trends for Hill numbers ($q = 0$, $q = 1$, $q = 2$) across climatic gradients. The upper panel (A) corresponds to models using mean annual precipitation (MAP) as the predictor, whereas the lower panel (B) corresponds to models using precipitation seasonality (PS). Solid lines represent predicted values from single-covariate mixed-effects models, and shaded bands indicate 95% confidence intervals. Hill numbers were standardized to a common sample size to ensure comparability among point counts. Labels indicating Significant denote predictors whose effects were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) in the corresponding single-covariate models and do not imply significance at individual data points.

Figure 8: Beta-coefficient plots summarizing the effects of precipitation seasonality on size-standardized Hill-number alpha diversity ($q=0$, $q = 1$, $q=2$) estimated at the alpha-point level across sampling scenarios (sampling level) corresponding to different effective spatial grains. Points represent estimated effects from single-covariate models, and horizontal bars indicate 95% confidence intervals. For GAM/GAMM models, coefficients summarize the overall direction and magnitude of the fitted relationship and should be interpreted alongside the corresponding trend plots. Effects whose confidence intervals do not overlap zero are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

774

775 Hypothesis 2: Climate positively influences aggregated community abundance

776

777 Climatic variables influence aggregated community abundance (ACA) in a number of ways.

778 ACA significantly declined with MAP and TS, suggesting a combined response to seasonality

779 and water availability (Figure 9, Appendix S3 Table S1). The modelled effects of MAP were

780 consistent negative across sampling scenarios with increased uncertainty (Appendix S3 Figures

781 S5). In contrast, MAT and PS did not influence ACA at any sampling scenario, with responses

782 showing high uncertainty at the second and first triad scenarios (Figure 9, Appendix S3 Figures
783 S6 and S7).

784 Hypothesis 3: Climate positively influences aggregated community biomass

785
786 Aggregated community biomass (CAB) was mostly insensitive to climatic variables (Appendix
787 S3 Table S1). Both MAP, MAT and TS did not significantly influence ACB across triad levels,
788 indicating that total community biomass did not change with rainfall and temperature (Appendix
789 S3 Figures S5-S6). Nevertheless, ACB significantly decreased with PS, showing that more
790 temporal variability in rainfall decreased total biomass (Appendix S3 Figure S7). This effect was
791 consistent but with higher uncertainty in the second and first triad scenarios (Appendix S3 Figure
792 S11).

793

794

795

Figure 9: Model-based predictions of community-level bird abundance estimated at the point-count (α -point) level. Panels A–D show predicted abundance trends across climatic covariates. Solid lines represent predictions from single-covariate negative binomial generalized linear mixed models, and shaded bands indicate 95% confidence intervals. Labels indicating Significant denote predictors whose effects were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) in the corresponding single-covariate models and do not imply significance at individual data points.

796

797 Hypothesis 4: Mean climate and climatic seasonality have differential effects on alpha diversity,
 798 abundance and biomass

799

800 Nested model comparisons revealed contrasting climatic controls on alpha diversity (Table 4).

801 Precipitation seasonality consistently outperformed mean annual precipitation across diversity

802 orders, whereas temperature effects were shared between mean and seasonal components, with

803 both contributing increasingly from richness to dominance.

804 Both climatic axes explained a small proportion of alpha-diversity variation overall, with minimal
805 explanatory power for richness and moderately higher—but still limited—contributions for
806 Shannon and Simpson diversity. The precipitation and temperature axes showed remarkably
807 similar patterns of explained variance across diversity orders, indicating comparable and
808 generally weak climatic control of alpha diversity along the gradient (Appendix S3, Tables S2-
809 S3).

810 For ACA, MAP dominated the effect, whereas PS had a stronger effect on ACB. The water
811 climatic axis explained only a very small variation of both community abundance and biomass
812 across the gradient (marginal $R^2 \approx 8\%$) (Appendix S3, Tables S4-S5).

813 The temperature effects on ACA and ACB was dominated by TS (Appendix S3, Tables S4-S5).

814 As in the case of the water axis, the temperature axis explained a very small fraction of the
815 variance for both community properties. (Appendix S3, Tables S4-S5).

816 Nested models across different sampling scenarios showed broadly consistent effects in both
817 direction and magnitude for the four climatic covariates—particularly mean annual precipitation
818 (MAP) and precipitation seasonality (PS)—on alpha diversity, aggregated community abundance
819 (ACA), and aggregated community biomass (ACB), albeit with increasing uncertainty at finer
820 effective spatial grains (Appendix S3, Tables S6–S17). Although some climatic predictors were
821 statistically significant in nested models (specially third triad scenario), these effects were
822 generally weak and consistent with the limited explanatory power observed in single-covariate
823 analyses. Together, both modelling phases indicate that climatic gradients exert modest and
824 scale-dependent effects on alpha diversity, without a single climatic axis emerging as a dominant
825 driver.

826 Sensitivity tests

827

828 Leave-one-site-out (LOSO) tests showed that excluding each site in turn generally did not alter
829 the direction or significance of mean annual precipitation (MAP), precipitation seasonality (PS),
830 or temperature seasonality (TS) effects on biomass and abundance. Parameter estimates
831 consistently fell within the 95% confidence bounds of the full sampling scenario, indicating that
832 in most of the cases no single forest site disproportionately influenced the detected climatic
833 relationships for most associations (Appendix S4).

834 Nonetheless, the effects of MAP changed with the removal of Campo Ma'an and Dja, confirming
835 an influence of these forest sites in model estimates (Appendix S4 figures S2 and S4). This
836 indicates that the effects of these climatic factors on community properties are influenced by
837 particular locations of the gradient. The effects of MAT, PS and TS on alpha diversity were not
838 influenced by the removal of Dja and Campo Mann (Appendix S4 figure S5).

839 Removing one climate data source (CHELSA, CHIRPS, CRU, or WorldClim) using (LODO)
840 yielded highly consistent MAP–diversity and structure relationships, both in direction and
841 magnitude. Effect estimates varied minimally among datasets and remained positive across Hill
842 numbers, or negative ACA and ACB (Appendix S5 figures S8-S10), confirming that the effects
843 of MAP on diversity, abundance and biomass are robust to uncertainties in rainfall estimation and
844 not driven by any single climate product.

845 Moran's I values for non-spatial model residuals indicated weak positive spatial autocorrelation
846 (SAC) at the α -scale (0.3 km; $I \approx 0.1$ – 0.2) but negligible or zero SAC at beta cluster (0.9 km) and
847 regional (> 350 km) scales respectively (Appendix S4, Table S1). These low values, together
848 with the inclusion of random intercepts for site and cluster, confirm that parameter estimates are
849 not biased by spatial dependence. These effects disappeared entirely once spatial smooths were
850 incorporated. Residuals from all spatial models showed Moran's $I \approx 0$ across alpha plots, beta
851 clusters, and regional scales (Appendix S4, Tables S2-S4).

852 Spatially explicit models confirmed that the strong climatic effects detected in non-spatial and
853 nested analyses were largely spatially structured across the regional gradient. When incorporating
854 spatial smooths of geographic coordinates, the effects of mean annual precipitation on diversity
855 remained directionally consistent but declined in magnitude, indicating that much of the MAP
856 signal covaries with geography along the regional gradient (Appendix S4, Tables S3-S4). Similar
857 patterns were observed for MAT, TS and PS, though these variables explained less variation
858 overall. Abundance responses were comparatively weaker and remained largely unaffected by
859 spatial structure, suggesting that their climatic sensitivity operates at finer scales (Appendix S4,
860 Table S1). However, the effects of PS on biomass and dominant species remained strong after
861 accounting for spatial structure (Appendix S4, Table S2, S4). Collectively, these analyses show
862 that the climatic effects on community properties are robust yet embedded within spatially
863 structured environmental gradients.

864 **Discussion**

865 To our knowledge, this is the first study to investigate macroecological patterns of tropical bird
866 communities and their climatic drivers along an extensive gradient using a fractal design. Our
867 results provide a detailed picture of community patterns across different sampling scenarios that
868 reflect different scales measured by effective spatial grain) and reveal how climate influences
869 tropical bird assemblages in contrasting ways depending on both the diversity component
870 considered and the spatial scale of analysis. Specifically, we found: (1) scale-dependent changes
871 in gamma and alpha diversity and community reorganization (RAC metrics) across sampling
872 scenarios, (2) relatively constant SADs across sites, (3) consistent but spatially structured
873 positive unimodal effects of MAP on diversity and weaker effects of MAT, as expected for a
874 precipitation gradient, 4) contrasting weak effects of MAP on aggregated community abundance

875 (ACA) but no effects on aggregated community biomass (ACB), and (5) that temporal variability
876 shape alpha diversity, ACA, and ACB in different ways (unimodal, linear). Below, we discuss the
877 implications of these findings for tropical macroecology and climate–diversity theory, as well as
878 the value of assessing spatial-scale dependence of macroecology patterns across different
879 sampling scenarios in regional gradients.

880 Shifts in gamma bird diversity along a tropical rainfall gradient

881
882 Characterizing macroecological patterns of forest bird communities along a tropical rainfall
883 gradient highlights their complexity when analyzed through the Hill numbers framework. Under
884 the full sampling scenario Gamma diversity (total richness, $q=0$) was rather similar across forest
885 locations, reflecting equally diverse regional species pools (Cornell and Harrison 2014; Jarzyna et
886 al. 2025). However, more variation was evident in Shannon and Simpson where the driest site
887 (Lobeke) was considerably lower, whereas the one with more precipitation seasonality (Mbam et
888 Djerem) was the most diverse, highlighting that dominance patterns vary with climate. Thus, Hill
889 number profiles provide complementary evidence that climate influences different facets of
890 gamma diversity in tropical lowland rainforests (see also Hypothesis 1 for alpha diversity).

891 These results of high gamma diversity are consistent with the view that humid lowland tropical
892 forests are hotspots of local diversity (Cooper et al. 2024; Hawkins et al. 2007; 2003; Myers et al.
893 2000; Rahbek and Graves 2001; Sabatini et al. 2022). However, they also suggest that high
894 within-site (Gamma) diversity is not homogeneously distributed across tropical lowland forests
895 and changes with variations in seasonality and mean rainfall and even temperature seasonality,
896 challenging assumptions from broad-scale studies (200×200 km, 100×100 km, and 50×50 km
897 grid cells) and those done in a single forest region (Jenkins et al. 2013; Jetz and Rahbek 2002;
898 Rahbek and Graves 2001; Martínez-Núñez et al. 2023; Rutt et al. 2023)).

899 At local scales, lowland bird communities within the same biogeographic regions subject to
900 similar climatic conditions often show comparable gamma and alpha diversity (Alonso et al.
901 2013; Blake 2007; Karr 1971; Martínez et al. 2023; Robinson et al. 2000; Terborgh et al. 1990;
902 Waltert et al. 2005). However, when communities are compared across contrasting climatic
903 conditions, within-site diversity varies more strongly (Burner et al. 2018; Echeverri et al. 2019;
904 Pearman 2002; Robinson et al. 2000; Rompré et al. 2007). Our results indicate that both patterns
905 occur within the Congo forest biome.

906 Comparative studies in central African rainforests remain scarce, yet our findings provide mixed
907 alignment with existing work. A long-term study in Gabon (Brosset and Erard 1986) reported
908 similar gamma and alpha diversity, species composition, and dominant taxa, especially compared
909 with our driest site (Lobeke), but it diverged more from other sites along our gradient. Likewise,
910 research around Korup National Park (Waltert et al. 2005) found high alpha diversity comparable
911 to some of our wetter locations (e.g., Campo Mann). The geographic proximity of these sites to
912 ours suggests that gamma patterns are broadly consistent in nearby areas of primary forest in
913 central Africa.

914 Overall, our results show that macroecological patterns of gamma diversity in tropical lowland
915 forests are more multifaceted and complex than previously assumed (Gentry 1988; Karr 1976;
916 Terborgh and Andresen 1998). While recent studies across tropical taxa—including plants
917 (Cooper et al. 2024; de Aledo et al. 2023; ter Steege et al. 2023), mammals (Ahumada et al.
918 2011), amphibians (Asad et al. 2022), and arthropods (Basset et al. 2015) showed changes in
919 diversity in tropical forest communities, we found that pattern of evenness and dominance of
920 whole tropical lowland bird communities more clearly emerge under the hill numbers framework.
921 Species richness alone cannot fully capture spatial macroecological patterns in tropical bird

922 communities and is more prone to error measurements and comparisons (Chao et al. 2014;
923 Roswell et al. 2021) . We expect similar patterns in other animal groups (e.g., mammals,
924 amphibians, reptiles, arthropods). Further macroecological research across lowland climatic
925 gradients is needed to build a more complete picture of tropical local diversity.

926 Abundance structure patterns in the rainfall gradient

927 Our study shows that the structure of tropical bird communities at the forest site level along the
928 rainfall gradient is complex and heterogeneous but with some striking consistencies at the broad
929 structural level (SADs). Across the gradient, SADs were remarkably similar, with the Poisson
930 lognormal model (Preston 1948) fitting nearly all sites. This suggests a consistent underlying
931 general structure in abundance distributions. The main exception was Mbam et Djerem, where a
932 log-series provided the best fit, likely reflecting the influence of the neighboring savanna pool or
933 stronger rainfall seasonality that increases the number of rare species.

934 The strong similarities in SADs across our study sites suggests that, within the range of variation
935 in climatic variables we measured, this metric of community structure does not show sufficient
936 variation to provide clues as to specific mechanistic drivers regulating patterns of abundance
937 across bird species. Previous research suggests that climate (e.g., temperature) strongly influences
938 SADs (Formoso-Freire et al. 2025; Matthews et al. 2019). We did not directly test climatic
939 effects on SADs here, but our findings highlight the need for further analyses of how specific
940 climatic factors shape SADs in tropical bird communities.

941 Our results reinforce the idea of a canonical SAD in terrestrial communities with low human
942 disturbance (Dornelas et al. 2014): a few species hold most individuals, while the majority is rare
943 (McGill et al. 2007). Previous work has shown near-universal SADs described by Poisson
944 lognormal or log-series across tropical animal and plant communities (Baldrige et al. 2016;

945 Callaghan et al. 2023; Rosindell and Cornell 2013; Ulrich et al. 2010). Syntheses for birds
946 indicate both models fit well, though Poisson lognormal is generally superior (Baldrige et al.
947 2016; Callaghan et al. 2023; Ulrich et al. 2010). For trees, studies in central African forests
948 (Cooper et al. 2024, 20) and the Amazon (ter Steege et al. 2013) found log-series to fit best. No
949 previous comparisons exist for multiple tropical bird communities, so our results provide new
950 evidence that Poisson lognormal better describes SADs of central African lowland bird
951 communities. Broader studies with standardized sampling will be required to test whether this
952 pattern holds across other gradients.

953 The dominance pattern within each site appears linked to a core set of consistently dominant
954 species, notably the Greenbulls *Eurillas virens*, *E. latirostris*, and the Olive sunbird *Cyanomitra*
955 *olivacea* dominates in all sites, while Grey Parrots (*Psittacus erithacus*), Green Pigeons (*Treron*
956 *calvus*) strongly *dominated* only in the driest site (Lobeke) and one large Hornbill (*Ceratogymna*
957 *atrata*) in the site with intermediate rainfall and seasonality (Dja) and the wettest one (Campo
958 Mann). Other common species shifted markedly in rank abundance across sites. In contrast, rare
959 and uncommon species comprised most of the species across all the sites. This pattern was found
960 by (Erard 1987; Brosset and Erard 1986) in forest bird communities in Gabon.

961 Community structure along the African rainfall gradient was more similar to that reported for
962 Cocha Cashu in the Peruvian Amazon than to lowland forests in Panama. In Panamanian forests,
963 community structure is characterized by a pronounced oligarchy, with several species reaching
964 very high abundances (often exceeding 100 individuals), resulting in strong numerical dominance
965 by a small subset of species (Robinson et al. 2000). In contrast, both African sites and Cocha
966 Cashu lack such a strong oligarchic structure: only one or two species reached comparable
967 abundance levels, while most common species occurred at substantially lower abundances and

968 communities were characterized by a high proportion of rare species (Terborgh et al. 1990).
969 Consistent with this pattern, average raw abundance summaries at 100 ha across the African sites
970 (~1,800 individuals) were closer in magnitude to values reported for Cocha Cashu (~1,700
971 individuals) than to those from Panama (~3,234 individuals). While sampling methods, temporal
972 scales, and detection processes differ among studies, these comparisons place African lowland
973 forests within a broader pantropical context and provide a useful benchmark for community
974 structure at the 100-ha scale.

975 The numerical dominance by a small “oligarchy” of species mirrors findings for trees in central
976 Africa (Rejou-Mechain et al. 2021), and for birds (Blake 2007; Martínez et al. 2023; Terborgh et
977 al. 1990) and trees (Cooper et al. 2024; ter Steege et al. 2013) in the Amazon basin, providing
978 preliminary support for the oligarchy hypothesis (Pitman et al. 2013; 2001). However, the
979 generality of this pattern revealed mainly in plants (Enquist et al. 2019) and its drivers remain
980 unclear for tropical birds and other animal groups (herbs, epiphytes) groups and warrant further
981 study.

982 Evenness profiles based on Hill numbers ($q = 1, 2$) showed pronounced differences along the
983 gradient: Lobeke (driest site) was highly uneven, while Campo Mann and Mbam et Djerem
984 (wetter sites) were more even and Dja forest bird community was in between. The extreme
985 unevenness in Lobeke likely reflects the hyperdominance of canopy frugivores such as Grey
986 Parrots (*Psittacus erithacus*) and Green Pigeons (*Treron calvus*), contrasting with understory
987 bulbuls and sunbirds dominating in the very wet and seasonal sites. In the Dja both rare and
988 common species contribute equally.

989 These findings show that evenness in tropical bird communities responds to rainfall and
990 seasonality in precipitation, paralleling results from more mesic habitats (Haviv et al. 2025).

991 They also highlight that commonness and rarity are not spatially homogeneous, echoing evidence
992 of heterogeneity in evenness across tropical birds (Robinson et al. 2000; 2021; Tinoco et al.
993 2021), plants (Hordijk et al. 2024; Van Der Sande et al. 2024), and arthropods (Gibb et al. 2015;
994 Nichols et al. 2007). Shifts in evenness may be shaped by local heterogeneity (Karr 1990;
995 Terborgh et al. 1990), disturbance history (Karr 1982), regional pool size (Ricklefs 2004),
996 competition (Oliveira et al. 2020), or dispersal limitation (Lees and Peres 2009; Moore et al.
997 2008). We did not evaluate these mechanisms here, but they warrant closer examination in
998 tropical rainfall gradients. Overall, our results indicate that while the broad form of SADs
999 remains constrained (McGill et al. 2007), internal reorganization of relative abundances—shifts
1000 in commonness and rarity—varies substantially with climate. This suggests that macroecological
1001 stability at the community level coexists with marked internal dynamics across tropical rainfall
1002 gradients.

1003 Scale-dependent patterns of gamma diversity and community structure

1004 The patterns of gamma diversity and community structure we described for the full sampling
1005 scenario changed markedly when examined across different sampling scenarios (third, second
1006 and first triad scenarios). Our first key finding is that gamma diversity patterns based on Hill
1007 numbers were strongly scale-dependent: diversity rankings of sites shifted with the sampling
1008 scenario considered. These results confirm the scale-dependence of diversity patterns (Cassey et
1009 al. 2006; Chase et al. 2019; Jarzyna and Jetz 2018; Levin 1992; Rahbek 2005; Wiens 1989)
1010 within the spatial scales covered by our gradient. Previous fractal studies in North American
1011 altitudinal gradients similarly found that different triad levels captured different amounts of
1012 variance in richness, Simpson diversity, and phylogenetic structure (Simpson and Pearse 2021).
1013 Our results extend these findings to the tropics, showing that Hill number profiles change with

1014 each sampling scenario, making the choice of a “best” scale subjective (Levin 1992). The full
1015 sampling scenario provided the most precise climate estimates and highest coverage, justifying its
1016 use to infer broad-scale patterns. Still, our findings argue for a multi-scale approach to local
1017 diversity in tropical gradients (Goh et al. 2024; Jarzyna and Jetz 2018; Rahbek 2005), both to
1018 capture regional variation and to assess how perceived patterns shift with spatial scale (Guo et al.
1019 2023; Levin 1992).

1020 This highlights the importance of assessing tropical macroecological patterns not only at coarse
1021 global or continental scales, but also at fine spatial resolutions where heterogeneity can be
1022 substantial (Brown 1995; Blackburn and Gaston 2002; Rosenzweig 1995; Stein et al. 2014).

1023 A second key result is that SADs at the site level remained relatively stable across sampling
1024 scenarios, even though gamma diversity varied strongly. This echoes previous work reporting
1025 SAD consistency across scales, suggesting that similar ecological mechanisms may underlie
1026 SADs and that they can potentially be extrapolated across larger areas within biomes (Borda-de-
1027 Água et al. 2012; Callaghan et al. 2023; Rosindell and Cornell 2013). The exception of Mbam et
1028 Djerem, however, indicates that historical context and proximity to adjacent biomes (e.g.,
1029 savanna) may alter broad community structure (Catano et al. 2025; Cornell and Harrison 2014;
1030 Koffel et al. 2022). To assess the pattern’s generality, we must test SAD variation in tropical
1031 systems—across key gradients such as rainfall and forest–savanna transitions—where evidence
1032 remains sparse relative to temperate datasets (Antão et al. 2021).

1033 A third important finding is that Hill number profiles and RAC metrics captured structural
1034 changes across sampling scenarios that were not visible in SADs. This suggests that internal
1035 reorganization of commonness and rarity occurs at different scales in tropical gradients, requiring
1036 a wide spectrum of metrics to fully describe community structure.

1037 Variation in evenness across scales represented in each sampling scenario likely reflects
1038 differences in sampling unit number, area covered, and spatial allocation. These factors determine
1039 how many species and individuals are captured, which is particularly important in tropical bird
1040 communities where many species are rare, spatially clumped, or wide-ranging (Karr 1971;
1041 Robinson et al. 2000; Terborgh et al. 1990), and where frugivores and insectivores often join
1042 mixed-species flocks (Goodale et al. 2015; Terborgh et al. 1990; Zou et al. 2018). We showed
1043 that capturing these complex spatial patterns requires both large spatial coverage and careful
1044 allocation of sampling units across environmental gradients. Our fractal design allowed us to
1045 maximize both, reinforcing the importance of broad-area sampling in tropical bird research
1046 (Robinson and Curtis 2020). Beyond area, however, our results emphasize the need to also
1047 capture environmental variation by allocating plots across spatial distances and sites.

1048 Influence of climate on alpha diversity, abundance and biomass across different sampling
1049 scenarios

1050 Our study provides the first test of the climate hypothesis in a lowland tropical rainfall gradient
1051 using a fractal design, offering unique insights into how climate affects alpha diversity,
1052 abundance, and biomass across scales.

1053 For our first hypothesis, we found a strong and consistent positive unimodal effect of rainfall
1054 (MAP) on alpha diversity, supporting a dominant role of water at regional scales. As expected,
1055 water availability rather than temperature explained diversity, consistent with global and
1056 continental macroecological studies emphasizing the importance of water in lowland tropical
1057 regions (Coelho et al. 2025; Bradford A. Hawkins et al. 2003). The shape of the response of
1058 diversity to rainfall changed with different Hill numbers (linear or unimodal) suggesting a more
1059 complex pattern of what has been reported for bird species responses to rainfall gradients using

1060 citizen science data (e.g., hump-shaped) (Freeman et al. 2024). Rainfall effects likely operate
1061 directly through physiological constraints on activity and metabolism (Gavrilov 2017; Molokwu
1062 et al. 2010; Wiersma et al. 2007; Wolfe et al. 2025), and indirectly through resource availability
1063 (plants, arthropods, fruits, flowers) and habitat conditions (Kaspari et al. 2000; Kissling et al.
1064 2007; Newell et al. 2023; Suttidate et al. 2019; Wolfe et al. 2025). We did not measure these
1065 mechanisms directly, but they are plausible pathways linking rainfall to bird diversity.

1066 Importantly, the response of alpha diversity to rainfall depended on the Hill number used. Mean
1067 annual precipitation did not influence richness ($q = 0$) but strongly influenced Shannon diversity
1068 ($q = 1$), and Simpson diversity ($q = 2$), indicating differential effects on rarity, evenness, and
1069 dominance. This highlights the critical role of Hill numbers in macroecological studies: relying
1070 on a single measure (e.g., richness) risks incomplete or misleading conclusions (Kusumoto et al.
1071 2023). Previous research has emphasized the value of multiple Hill numbers for capturing
1072 responses to abiotic, biotic, and human drivers (Arnold et al. 2021; Chazdon et al. 2022;
1073 Kortmann et al. 2025), and our results confirm their necessity for hypothesis testing in tropical
1074 environmental gradients.

1075 Our results further show the importance of using size-standardized Hill numbers to assess alpha
1076 diversity when sample coverage is low or highly heterogeneous at the point count level which
1077 reduces the usefulness of standardized coverage in these small sampling units. This is particularly
1078 true in very diverse tropical forest bird communities where the area covered by a single point
1079 count is too small to cover the territories of a very large fraction of the species in the community
1080 (Karr 1971; Terborgh et al. 1990). Previous research with tropical forest bird communities
1081 showed that very small areas are not able to fully characterize community diversity (Robinson et
1082 al. 2000; Blake 2007; Terborgh et al. 1990; Karr 1976). Therefore, a very high number of

1083 singletons (species with abundance of one) are expected in individual point counts generating low
1084 coverage and high coverage deficit (Chao and Jost 2012), making sample coverage not very
1085 practical at this sampling level in primary tropical lowland forests. Therefore, we suggest
1086 carefully strongly replicating spatially and temporally individual point counts. Our results
1087 showed that even with high temporal replication patterns of alpha diversity in tropical bird
1088 communities should be taken conservative. Hence, estimators for the effective number of species
1089 that are standardized by number of individuals (Chao et al. 2014), which can change among point
1090 counts (Ralph et al. 1995) can be helpful for comparing alpha diversity patterns in very rich
1091 tropical bird communities. Nonetheless, we highlight that more research is required in this
1092 direction.

1093 For the second hypothesis, contrary to theoretical expectations of “more individuals with more
1094 water or energy” (Karl L. Evans et al. 2005; Wright 1983), aggregated community abundance
1095 (ACA) declined with rainfall and was unaffected by temperature. Thus, our results do not support
1096 the “more individuals–more species” hypothesis (Srivastava and Lawton 1998). Instead, they
1097 suggest that diversity and abundance are decoupled in this gradient, as found in other studies
1098 (Currie et al. 2004; Hurlbert and Jetz 2010; Storch et al. 2018). Richer communities tended to
1099 have fewer individuals, consistent with stronger niche packing under high water availability
1100 (Hurlbert 2004; Pigot et al. 2016; Storch et al. 2008) or greater climatic stress enhancing
1101 hyperabundance of a few tolerant species (Davey et al. 2012). However, the effect of rainfall on
1102 abundance was weaker than its effect on alpha diversity, suggesting that additional mechanisms
1103 regulate total individual numbers in tropical bird communities.

1104 For the third hypothesis, in contrast with alpha diversity and abundance, aggregated community
1105 biomass (ACB) was not significantly influenced by either rainfall or temperature. This suggests

1106 that while richness and abundance respond to the amount of energy and water, total community
1107 energy remains constant. The only climatic factor that influenced biomass was precipitation
1108 seasonality, which weakly reduced ACB in non-spatial models, but strongly in spatial models
1109 suggesting that more seasonality in rainfall can reduce the abundance of large-bodied species that
1110 contribute most to biomass. Previous research showed that rainforest bird abundance can strongly
1111 respond to seasonality in rainfall (Williams and Middleton 2008). However, its effects on total
1112 community biomass are not clear. This underscores the need to explore how temporal variability
1113 influences bird biomass in tropical regions. Relatively stable biomass may result from
1114 compensatory dynamics (Gonzalez and Loreau 2009), where high abundances of large-bodied
1115 species such as hornbills offset changes in smaller species. Few previous studies have examined
1116 biomass in this context, making comparisons difficult, but our results point to a critical research
1117 frontier: understanding how animal community-level biomass responds to environmental
1118 gradients in the tropics.

1119 Our multi-scale design revealed that the effects of climate varied with spatial scale measured by
1120 effective spatial grain in each sampling scenario. Rainfall effects on alpha diversity were scale-
1121 dependent, with both direction and shape shifting across sampling scenarios, indicating that
1122 detecting how climate shapes diversity depends on the spatial grain (particularly effective spatial
1123 grain) of analysis (Belmaker and Jetz 2011; Gaston and Blackburn 2010) even at very fine spatial
1124 grains.

1125 In contrast, rainfall effects on abundance were more consistent across scales represented by
1126 different sampling scenarios, suggesting that abundance-climate relationships may be
1127 generalizable at fine grains (Karl L. Evans et al. 2005; Hurlbert 2004). Biomass responses along
1128 the gradient were variable, and decoupled from diversity, contrary to theoretical expectations

1129 (Pigot et al. 2025). While past studies have reported both consistent and variable climate effects
1130 across scales (Evans et al. 2005; Hawkins et al. 2003; Kaspari et al. 2003), none to our
1131 knowledge have tested multi-scale effects on diversity, abundance, and biomass in tropical bird
1132 communities. Our results therefore highlight the importance of explicitly incorporating scale via
1133 different sampling scenarios when evaluating macroecological hypotheses in regional tropical
1134 gradients.

1135 Finally, cross-validation analyses (LODO and LOSO) conducted on the full sampling scenario
1136 showed that the detected climatic effects are not driven by any single forest site or climatic
1137 dataset (e.g., WorldClim, CHELSA). At the same time, cross-validation revealed that MAP
1138 effects are sensitive to the removal of individual sites, reflecting heterogeneous site leverage
1139 along the rainfall gradient. In contrast, precipitation seasonality and temperature showed
1140 consistent support across folds, particularly for dominance-weighted diversity ($q = 2$). LODO
1141 analyses further indicate a degree of spatial nonstationarity (Foody 2004) in some relationships,
1142 highlighting that climatic effects vary across space rather than being spatially uniform. Together,
1143 these results demonstrate that cross-validation provides critical insight into the spatial structure
1144 and robustness of climatic relationships in tropical regional gradients.

1145 Spatial models further revealed that the regional rainfall gradient is strongly spatially structured,
1146 with climate covarying smoothly across geographic space. This reinforces the notion that
1147 disentangling spatial and climatic effects is inherently challenging (Gaspard et al. 2019; Bradford
1148 A. Hawkins et al. 2003; Ploton et al. 2020; Viana et al. 2022) in geographically structured
1149 gradients such as the Central African rainfall gradient, and supports the view that the geography
1150 of climate plays a central role in shaping diversity patterns (Coelho et al. 2023). Our findings
1151 therefore highlight the importance of incorporating spatial models when analyzing regional

1152 environmental gradients to avoid over-attributing stronger effects to climate alone or other factors
1153 (Kim and Shin 2016; Ploton et al. 2020). Nevertheless, we emphasize that spatial analyses should
1154 be implemented in combination with cross-validation approaches to assess the robustness of
1155 climatic signals and improve the interpretability of macroecological patterns.

1156 Relative effects of mean and temporal variance on alpha diversity, abundance and biomass
1157 patterns

1158 Our study of the rainfall gradient showed interestingly that seasonality in precipitation dominates
1159 the influence on community properties at the alpha point level, but it also highlights the still
1160 importance of mean annual precipitation, indicating the complementary roles of both aspects in
1161 shaping alpha diversity, abundance, and biomass. Both precipitation and temperature seasonality
1162 strongly influenced these properties in multiple ways (both linear and unimodal shapes),
1163 underscoring the need to account for climatic variability, not just mean values, when studying
1164 tropical ecological communities. Previous macroecological studies across altitudinal and
1165 latitudinal gradients have similarly emphasized the role of seasonality, although with differing
1166 outcomes (Ferber et al. 2017; Illán et al. 2014; Jarzyna and Stagge 2023; Keyser et al. 2024). Our
1167 results extend this evidence to tropical lowland rainfall gradients, showing that seasonality effects
1168 alter community structure.

1169 Seasonality in rainfall and temperature likely matters for tropical birds because it affects the
1170 availability of food resources (flowers, fruits, arthropods) (Bender et al. 2017; J. R. Karr 1976;
1171 Loiselle and Blake 1991; Newell et al. 2023) and alters microclimatic conditions for nesting,
1172 parental care and thermoregulation (Carroll et al. 2018; Perez et al. 2020; Zuckerberg et al. 2018).
1173 However, their effects in lowland tropical rainfall gradients remain poorly understood. Our
1174 findings therefore provide a basis for future research exploring how seasonality (both macro and

1175 micro climate) influences tropical bird communities, which in turn may improve predictions of
1176 their vulnerability to global environmental change.

1177 Finally, our results suggest that each climatic axis (MAP and PS; MAT and TS) together
1178 explained a very small proportion (25-30%) of variation in diversity across the gradient and
1179 considerably even less (8-9%) for community-level abundance and biomass. This indicates that
1180 climate alone does not fully account for the observed patterns, and that additional drivers are
1181 needed to explain the macroecological pattern. Past research and theory have highlighted the
1182 importance of biotic interactions (Freeman et al. 2022; Hembry and Weber 2020; Pigot et al.
1183 2018), historical processes (speciation, extinction, dispersal) (Harvey et al. 2020; Ricklefs 2004),
1184 biogeographic context (Pigot et al. 2018), and spatial distance (Graco-Roza et al. 2022) in
1185 shaping diversity patterns. Although our study focused solely on climate, these findings
1186 underscore the need to assess multiple mechanisms when investigating tropical environmental
1187 gradients to fully understand the origins and maintenance of biodiversity.

1188 The value of hybrid nested fractals for understanding macroecology patterns and testing theories
1189 in tropical gradients

1190 The hybrid fractal design we implemented for the first time in the Afrotropics offers new
1191 opportunities for studying macroecological patterns in regional tropical gradients. First, the
1192 inclusion of novel design elements improved species and individual capture and reduced
1193 uncertainty in effect estimates. Earlier fractal designs made important advances in characterizing
1194 beta diversity and diversity change at fine spatial scales (Marsh and Ewers 2013; Olivier and van
1195 Aarde 2014; Simpson and Pearse 2021), but typically emphasized peripheral points and did not
1196 incorporate central locations within the fractals. By contrast, our hybrid design expands the

1197 analytical possibilities, enabling simultaneous exploration of within- and between-community
1198 patterns.

1199 Second, the hybrid fractal (full sampling scenario) provided a baseline reference for comparing
1200 with other sampling scenarios (triad levels), offering a new framework for quantifying scale-
1201 dependence in diversity. Particularly relevant in our study is the manipulation in the sampling
1202 design of the effective spatial grain across different sampling scenarios. This parameter changes
1203 the scale at which community data is aggregated (Wiens 1989) allowing to capture different
1204 amounts of heterogeneity in each sampling scenario, while keeping constant spatial extent
1205 (spatial domain of the sampling) and basic spatial grain (area sampled by an individual sampling
1206 unit). This makes it possible to control for the effects of changing the spatial extent which
1207 unavoidably modify the species pool sampled, confounding the detection of gamma, beta and
1208 alpha patterns across scales (Dungan et al. 2002; Wiens 1989). This also makes it particularly
1209 difficult to explore what are the roles of both area and spatial distance in shaping these patterns.
1210 Both problems are well known in spatial ecology but often neglected by ecologists (Dungan et al.
1211 2002; Levin 1992; Turner 1990; Wiens 1989). Likewise, changing the basic spatial grain
1212 unavoidable changes the number of individuals sampled in each individual sampling unit,
1213 obscuring the patterns detected across scales (Wiens 1989; Dungan et al. 2002).

1214 In contrast, manipulating effective spatial grain across sampling scenarios allows us to examine
1215 how changes in the spatial aggregation of individuals and communities—drawn from the same
1216 site-level species pool and sampled at a constant basic grain—affect the detection of
1217 macroecological patterns and the evaluation of ecological hypotheses. Under this framework, the
1218 full sampling scenario provides a reference condition, representing the expected pattern in the
1219 absence of changes (Hairston 1989) in effective spatial grain when the highest sampling intensity

1220 in a particular study is deployed. The reduced triad scenarios (third, second, and first triads) can
1221 be interpreted as contrasting treatments, in which effective spatial grain is systematically altered
1222 while spatial extent and sampling protocol are held constant.

1223 This structure gives the sampling design a quasi-experimental character, making it particularly
1224 well suited for exploring spatial scaling in community ecology and macroecology. We
1225 emphasize, however, that the design is not fully experimental, as treatments are not randomly
1226 assigned to sampling units and classical elements such as blocking are not implemented (Hairston
1227 1989; Hurlbert 1984). Nevertheless, the design provides a flexible foundation upon which
1228 experimental elements could be incorporated in future studies, highlighting its potential
1229 contribution to emerging approaches in experimental macroecology (Alexander et al. 2016).

1230 Third, expanding the area of the fractals and increasing distances between sampling points
1231 enhanced statistical power and enabled robust tests of climatic effects on diversity at
1232 macroecological scales. While past fractal applications prioritized more triads at smaller scales
1233 (Simpson and Pearse 2021), our hybrid design complements these efforts by extending fractal
1234 sampling into larger spatial domains relevant for macroecology, while still retaining resolution
1235 for community ecology questions at local scales.

1236 Fourth, reducing effective spatial grain necessarily reduces the number of sampling units
1237 available for inference, leading to lower statistical power at finer sampling scenarios.

1238 Importantly, this reduction in power is systematic and identical across all sites, as the same fractal
1239 subsets were deployed consistently along the environmental gradient. Consequently, inter-site
1240 comparisons using our sampling design are not confounded by unequal sampling effort or
1241 replication.

1242 This controlled reduction in power implies that, rather than focusing exclusively on statistical
1243 significance (p-values) (Nakagawa and Cuthill 2007) across sampling scenarios—which is an
1244 unavoidable consequence of changing spatial grain—the key inferential focus should be on
1245 tracking changes in the direction and magnitude of effects across scales. Such comparisons allow
1246 assessment of how consistently a given ecological mechanism operates as effective spatial grain
1247 changes.

1248 This characterization of mechanism behavior across scales is particularly valuable in ecology for
1249 building causal understanding and for reinforcing transposability, defined as the ability to
1250 extrapolate a relationship to other conditions (Grace 2024). Accordingly, we recommend that
1251 studies of regional environmental gradients move beyond asking only whether relationships
1252 remain statistically significant across spatial scales, and instead assess how consistent or scale-
1253 dependent the estimated effects are.

1254 In our case, several relationships detected under the full sampling scenario were statistically
1255 significant but became non-significant as statistical power decreased at finer sampling scenarios,
1256 despite showing similar effect directions and overlapping confidence intervals. Consistent with
1257 recent calls in ecology to move beyond p-values and place greater emphasis on effect sizes and
1258 uncertainty (Wasserstein and Lazar 2016; Johnson 1999; Nakagawa and Cuthill 2007), we
1259 interpret our results across sampling scenarios primarily in terms of effect magnitude, direction,
1260 and confidence intervals rather than statistical significance alone.

1261 Hence, the hybrid fractal framework opens new opportunities to investigate mechanisms across
1262 scales considering multiple sampling scenarios. In our case, this design allowed us to assess how
1263 climate influences diversity, abundance, and biomass at different levels of effective spatial grain.
1264 More broadly, this capacity to link processes across scales directly addresses a long-standing goal

1265 in ecology: to integrate mechanisms of community organization with macroecological patterns
1266 (Brown 1999; Grace 2024,; Lawton 1999).

1267 Limitations and future challenges

1268 Our study is not free of limitations and challenges. First, we notice the strong tradeoff to
1269 implement large gamma fractals in tropical environmental gradients, indicating that deploying
1270 large fractals to cover suitable areas for sampling tropical bird communities will come at the cost
1271 of reducing the number of fractals feasible to implement in large regional gradients. We deployed
1272 four gamma fractals (16 beta clusters, 144 sampling Alpha points) across the gradient, therefore
1273 more future work will be required to evaluate the generality of our results with more gamma
1274 fractals (and hence beta clusters) in different locations, and we advise researchers to consider the
1275 tradeoffs in their study systems. Second, we measured diversity in a short temporal frame (2
1276 years), indicating the need to expand the temporal sampling in the fractals to evaluate how the
1277 patterns we detected change across time (temporal patterns and trends). Third, our study was
1278 focused only on birds, implying the necessity to investigate the macroecological patterns we
1279 discuss in other taxonomic groups. Moreover, beta diversity was not explicitly analyzed in this
1280 study implying the need to explore spatial turnover with deeper detail. Despite these challenges,
1281 we consider that sampling large areas with fractals as previous research and our study shows can
1282 provide several benefits for community ecology and macroecology.

1283 **Conclusions**

1284 Our study provides detailed insights into macroecological patterns of tropical forest bird
1285 communities along a lowland rainfall gradient in Cameroon. We found that diversity, abundance
1286 and biomass patterns of forest bird communities are scale-dependent, while the broad structure of

1287 SADs is scale invariant but internal structure is more dynamic. This suggests the need to explore
1288 biodiversity patterns across different spatial scales in tropical regional gradients. We also show
1289 that climate (particularly rainfall both its mean and seasonality) modulates alpha diversity and
1290 weakly influences abundance but not biomass, and that climate effects are scale-dependent and
1291 strongly spatially structured, highlighting the necessity to characterize climatic effects across
1292 spatial scales and taking into account spatial factors. Overall, we show that our hybrid fractal
1293 design is useful for characterizing macroecological patterns and exploring mechanism operation
1294 across scales in regional gradients. Our sampling design allows us to manipulate how much of the
1295 site-level community is captured by varying the effective spatial grain and other landscape-scale
1296 features, while holding spatial extent and basic spatial grain constant. Therefore, we believe that
1297 studying regional gradients with hybrid fractal designs can open new exciting research frontiers
1298 in macroecology and community ecology.

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1315

1316 **Author contributions**

1317 Andres Angulo R conceived the hybrid fractal design. Andres Angulo R, Matthias Waltert and
1318 Holger Kreft designed the study. Andres Angulo R coordinated and implemented the sampling
1319 design and all data collection. Francis Njie Motombi collected bird data. Douglas Robinson,
1320 Dylan Craven and Serge Bobo Kadiri provided essential conceptual, methodological and
1321 analytical inputs for study design and data analysis. Andres Angulo R compiled and analyzed the
1322 data. Andres Angulo R wrote the draft and edited the manuscript. All authors contributed to all
1323 the sections of the final version.

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1325

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1992 **Table 1:** Summary of sampling scenarios and spatial scaling parameters used in the study. Spatial
 1993 extent and basic spatial grain were held constant across all sampling scenarios, while effective
 1994 spatial grain—the number and spatial aggregation of sampling units within a fixed extent—was
 1995 varied by design.

Sampling scenario	Sampling points per site	Basic spatial grain	Spatial extent	Spatial configuration	Proportion of spatial extent sampled	Effective spatial grain (ha)	Inter-plot distances
Full sampling	36	~3 ha	~3.16 km ²	Three equilateral triangles (10 points each) + one central hexagon (6 points)	35.7	113	300 m (within clusters); 450 m (central hexagon)
Third triad	27	~3 ha	~3.16 km ²	Three equilateral triangles	26.85	84	300 m (within clusters); 900 m (between clusters)
Second triad	9	~3 ha	~3.16 km ²	All points separated by 900 m	8.95	28	900 m
First triad	3	~3 ha	~3.16 km ²	All points separated by 2,700 m	2.98	9	2,700 m

1997 **Table 2 Taxonomic richness across forest sites along the rainfall gradient.**

Site	Observed gamma_species	N orders	N families	N genera
Mbam	123	11	35	82
Lobeke	120	14	38	84
Dja	118	14	37	84
Campo Ma'an	107	11	36	76

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2010 **Table 3. Single-covariate models for Hill-number alpha diversity**

2011 Results of single-covariate models testing climatic effects on Hill-number alpha diversity ($q = 0,$
 2012 1, 2). Reported values correspond to slope (β) estimates for focal predictor variables. Model types
 2013 vary among responses and are indicated explicitly. Intercept terms are omitted for clarity.

Predictor	Hill number (q)	Model type	β estimate	Test statistic / smooth	p-value
MAP	q = 0	Gaussian GLMM	-0.63	–	0.110
MAP	q = 1	Quadratic GAMM	4.94	–	0.0177
MAP	q = 2	Quadratic GAMM	-2.64	–	0.080
PS	q = 0	Linear GAMM	1.07	t = 2.76	0.006
PS	q = 1	Linear GAMM	1.43	t = 3.12	0.002
PS	q = 2	Linear GAMM	1.78	t = 3.57	< 0.001
MAT	q = 0	Gaussian GLMM	-1.387	z = -3.68	< 0.001
MAT	q = 1	Gaussian GLMM	-1.826	z = -1.80	0.072
MAT	q = 2	Gaussian GLMM	-0.095	z = -1.31	0.191
TS	q = 0	Linear GAMM	0.208	t = 1.97	0.051
TS	q = 1	Quadratic GAMM	0.074	t = 2.28	0.024
TS	q = 2	Quadratic GAMM	0.145	t = 2.48	0.014

2014 **Note:** For GAM and quadratic GAMM models, predictor effects are represented by smooth or
2015 polynomial terms; standard errors and test statistics for individual β coefficients are therefore not
2016 reported (-). Significance is assessed using F-tests (or χ^2 tests) for the smooth or quadratic term.
2017 Statistically significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are shown in bold.

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2035 **Table 4. Relative importance of climatic axes from nested model comparisons**

2036 Results of nested model comparisons evaluating the relative importance of mean and seasonality
 2037 components of precipitation and temperature for size-standardized Hill-number alpha diversity (q
 2038 = 0, 1, 2). The table summarizes which climatic component received stronger support within each
 2039 climatic axis. Full model outputs, coefficients, and test statistics are provided in the Appendix S3
 2040 Table S2-S3.

Hill number (q)	Precipitation axis (MAP vs PS)	Temperature axis (MAT vs TS)	Overall support
$q = 0$ (richness)	Precipitation seasonality (PS) > MAP	Mean annual temperature (MAT) > TS	Significant
$q = 1$ (common species)	Precipitation seasonality (PS) \gg MAP	MAT + TS	Significant
$q = 2$ (dominant species)	Precipitation seasonality (PS) \gg MAP	MAT + TS	Significant

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